

inDICES

Measuring the Impact of Digital Culture

Deliverable 1.2

Data Register

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D1.2 – Data Register

Version 1.0

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Glossary

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1. Executive summary

This deliverable aims to offer an illustration of the web-based datasets that have been gathered up to M21 by the WP1 working group accessing a plurality of sources, and using a plurality of technologies. The purpose of this data is to provide a multitude of alternative views for the monitoring and analysis of the digitalization of cultural production.

We describe in detail the data sources that can be used to unravel the user (individual and organizational) behavior on the web related to cultural participation,, and in parallel also the data sources that allow for following and understanding the emerging participation trends in news portals and online social networks via WLT Visual Analytic Dashboard.

The analysis of these data sources can be informed by a set of domain-relevant keywords, web URLs, social media accounts identifying the cultural actors populating the digital space (as described in D1.4). To ensure reproducibility of our results, here it is presented the rationale behind the curation of these lists.

In this deliverable we also present a discussion of the limitations and advantages inherent with the various sources of data we identified, that might be, we hope, a useful reference for all stakeholders who will want to adapt our data gathering methodologies (discussed in D1.3) and our methodological toolbox (discussed in D1.1).

Finally, we report the organizational scheme that would guide our plans for integrating these datasets into the Open Observatory and release them to the public, when possible as open data.

2. Objectives

The objective of this deliverable is to provide a technical report describing the structure and characteristics of the data gathered between M1 and M21, and draw an organizational scheme that allows for their effective accessibility into the Observatory Platform.

The objectives of this deliverable are complementary to those of D1.3 and D1.4, in which are respectively discussed the parallel objectives of (i) reporting which data has been gathered at M14 and M21 and (ii) the methodological aspects of the process of data gathering, and some results arising from the analysis of the data. Future developments of the analyses based on the data presented here will be included in D1.5. Here, we instead deepen the details about the structure of the data by describing what information is available, their metadata, the licencing, how it has been collected and who are the stakeholders who could be interested in accessing that data.

We further provide a discussion on the usefulness and limitations of these datasets in the context of inDICES with specific information on the quality, reliability and accessibility of the data gathered. This comprises their connection with the indicators developed between M1 and M15, that can be found in D1.1, the integration of the data with the Observatory Platform, and information regarding the Visual Analytical Dashboard. Accompanying the technical discussion of this deliverable, and aiming at showing the utility of the data, we also offer some short use cases from different types of collected datasets (either manually accessed, automatically downloaded, or crawled by the Dashboard).

We describe, along with the data collection, the details of the data storage as of M21. The datasets collected in the context of the inDICES project, license permitting, will be made open, by the end of the project, in the Data Repository, with the goal of facilitating the discovery, reproducibility and the reuse of the data gathered, and sharing of the project's results by the inDICES target groups, namely Policy Makers, Cultural Heritage/Creative Sector Practitioners and Researchers. The Repository is currently under development, and we report in this deliverable its state, as well as the design process in which we have been involved in the last months.

3. Sources Description

In this section, we provide a description of the different datasets collected up to M21, describing their different characteristics in terms of sources, size and format, information provided and temporal framing, ownership, possible users and applicable indicators.

We divide this section into three parts. We first list in section 3.1 the data collected at FBK, whose primary goal has been to unravel the user (individual and organizational) behavior on the web. Then, in section 3.2, we describe the data gathered at WLT, whose main goal has been to follow and understand different trends in news portals and online social networks. Finally, in section 3.3, we discuss the rationale that has been chosen for the curation of a set of domain-relevant keywords, web URLs, social media accounts (namely, the so called “trend indicators” and the “case studies lists”) identifying the cultural actors populating the digital space.

3.1. Data Collected at FBK

Wikipedia

Wikipedia is a popular online encyclopedia containing free multilingual content released under an open license crowdsourced by a very active and collaborative community of editors.

What information is in this data?

As was discussed also in D1.3, Wikipedia is one of the largest platforms sharing Creative commons works, and this data provides an overview on a specific type of content that has characterized Web 2.0: the so-called free digital encyclopedias. Specifically, the Wikipedia datasets we collected include information on the creation and edition history of those hyperlinks allowing passage from a Wikipedia article to another. In particular, it is recorded, each time that a link is manually created or removed, thus excluding *transcluded links*, i.e. links automatically generated by templates defined in another page, which usually create all possible links within a given group of articles, producing big cliques and artificially inflating the density of connections. It is also recorded who created the link, either a registered user with his/her user name or an anonymous editor. Moreover, we track the information of the page name and if the hyperlink has been added towards another page or towards a section of another page.

What is the size of the data set?

The hyperlinks information for the Italian, Spanish and English versions of Wikipedia were downloaded and processed to be readily available for analysis. Different datasets were created (see Table below, with their names and sizes in compressed GB).

Dataset	Enwiki	Eswiki	Itwiki
<i>Raw Wikilinks</i>	746	111	92
<i>Raw Wikilinks Snapshots</i>	36	8	9
<i>Resolved Redirects</i>	4	1	1
<i>Revisionlist</i>	62	9	8
<i>Snapshots</i>	42	8	6
<i>Wikilinks Graph</i>	21	4	4
Total	911	141	120

The different data sets in the Table are described in the following;

- Raw Wikilinks: This data set contains the hyperlinks between the articles, plus a bunch of other data, such as information about the user that added the link, the timestamp of the creation, what is the ID of the article that has been modified, etc.
- Raw Wikilinks Snapshots: Same as the previous data set, but limited to yearly snapshots.
- Resolved Redirects: *Redirects* are those pages that represent an alternative title for an article, e.g., <https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/MoMa> is a redirect of https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Museum_of_Modern_Art, so the former leads to the latter wikipedia article. We want to keep the principal article and their redirects as a single node in the network. In all the data sets, *redirects* have been tracked and resolved according to their timestamp. This information is stored in the Resolved Redirects data set.
- Revisionlist: Data set containing the list of all revisions for each article. A *revision* is created every time an edit is made.
- Wikilinks Graph: Dataset containing information the article from which a hyperlink departs from and the article at which the hyperlink arrives to. This is given as the identifier given automatically in the WikiDumps and as page titles.
- Snapshots: Same as the previous data set, but limited to yearly snapshots.

Where does it come from?

The data are provided by Wikimedia through the Wikidump portal. The data collection was performed via a script, modified from [C. Consonni, et al., Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media, 13

2019], that downloads the dump files, in XML format. A pipeline was devised: first the data collection, then the processing of raw data and finally we made use of Azure Batch, a cloud service to run in parallel several processes in an automated and very efficient way for storage.

Data Type/Format:

The final format of the processed data is CSV. For the storage of the processed data, we decided to adopt Azure's object storage because it offers unlimited space, it is object-based as well as cost-effective (see D1.1 and D1.3 for the detailed process).

Publication Date

The English, Spanish and Italian Wikipedia have all been active since 2001 and we recorded the evolution of the hyperlinks up to 1st May 2020.

How often is it updated?

The Wikidump portal is updated twice a month. At the beginning of the month all information historical revision is updated, while a second dump, starting the 20th of the month contains only the current revisions. Our collection has been however done only once, as the process is very demanding and the evolution of the network relatively slow.

Who owns it (rights statement if applicable)/License:

Wikimedia Foundation's mission is to create educational content that is freely available to all people. In keeping with that goal, all information on Wikimedia projects may be freely shared, copied, remixed, and used for any purpose in perpetuity. All datasets we collected and processed therefore also follow this criteria under a CC BY-SA licence.

What indicators might apply?

This dataset allows for the use of indicators borrowed from Network Science. Indeed, using this data, we can reconstruct networks defined by the hyperlinks between wikipedia pages. Using standard indicators from Networks Analysis such as community detection methods, it is possible to identify articles that are central for a specific topic and articles that bridge between different topics. Having a complete temporal overview of the evolution of the network, it is further possible to isolate the most natural connections between concepts as those that appeared the earliest.

IMDb

IMDb is a popular online database comprising information about movies, tv-shows, video games, and streaming content online.

What information is in this data?

For each title included in IMDb, it is listed a wide range of information including cast, production crew and personal biographies, plot summaries, trivia, box office, ratings, and fan and critical reviews.

What is the size of the data set?

It contains more than 8 million titles (visit <https://www.imdb.com/pressroom/stats/> for other statistics). The whole data collected is close to 75GB of data.

Where does it come from?

The data is collected through the IMDb API via an automated script and stored automatically in Azure.

Data Type/ Format:

We produced and stored CSV files.

Publication Date

IMDb It was launched online in 1990, and has been a subsidiary of Amazon since 1998.

How often is it updated?

The dataset is currently being updated on a weekly basis.

Who owns it (rights statement if applicable)/License:

All data is the property of IMDb, which grants its users a limited, non-exclusive, non-transferable, non-sublicensable license to access and make personal and non-commercial use of the IMDb Services. The code used to download the data will be made available.

What indicators might apply?

We can study the IMDb data from the perspective of time series analysis and network science. From the former, because we have longitudinal data about the careers of the directors, actors/actresses, etc, as well as the time evolution of the rating of the films. Since we also have access to the casts, the collaborations between actors can be tracked and mapped to a temporal collaboration network. If this data set is enriched with extra information, such as the revenue of the films, extra indicators could be used, such as those on economic impact.

TikTok

TikTok is an online social platform released in 2016 where users share short-form videos. In just a few years, it has become one of the most used worldwide, ranking first among the most downloaded free apps for long periods of time.

What information is in this data?

For each video posted on the platform we have information at the level of both the user and the video content, such as the video creation time-stamp, the text accompanying the video, number of comments and likes, the creator username. We also have a link pointing towards the video. Unless the video has been deleted by the users, also the video content can be accessed and downloaded.

What is the size of the data set?

In this dataset we have the information corresponding to 25,000,000 TikTok videos from 6,973,120 unique users, who might be associated with a TikTok Challenge if they have participated in it (26,245 of unique challenges in our dataset). The final CSV file is 5.7GB.

Where does it come from?

We downloaded the data from <https://files.pushshift.io/>.

Data Type/ Format:

The original data comes in JSON format and we have processed and filtered it creating a final CSV file.

Publication Date

The data cover the period from October 2016 to December 2019.

How often is it updated?

This dataset cannot be updated.

Who owns it (rights statement if applicable)/License:

This dataset can be shared with the proper acknowledgment of the original source (CC-BY).

What indicators might apply?

This dataset allows for the use of indicators borrowed from Network Science. Indeed, this dataset allows us to reconstruct networks describing different kinds of interactions, e.g., direct interactions via user mentions in the text, or indirect

interactions via communities of practice for those participating in the same challenges.

DeviantArt

DeviantArt is an online social community, founded in 2000. This platform was created to exhibit, promote, and share pieces of art, from literature, painting and sculpture to digital art, pixel art, films, and anime.

What information is in this data?

We have the link pointing to the artwork plus a bunch of metadata. Regarding the user that uploads the artwork, we know its ID and whether or not it is a regular or premium user (DevianArt categories). Regarding the artwork, we know when it was uploaded, if the content is considered for adults-only, the dimensions of the artwork, and some statistics, such as the number of comments and the number of times an artwork has been flagged as favorite.

We do not have direct access to the text accompanying the artworks, but can be retrieved as long as the artwork has not been deleted. The same applies for the artwork itself, which can be accessed and downloaded in the uploaded format (png, jpg, etc.)

What is the size of the data set?

We currently have collected 780GB of data.

Where does it come from?

We prepared an automated script that downloads the information regarding the most popular artworks proposed by DevianArt's API, according to their own criteria, and the most popular artworks of a certain number of fixed categories chosen by us.

Data Type/ Format

This data set comes in JSON and parquet format, one file per day. It has not been pre-processed and converted into structured CSV files yet.

Publication Date

The data have been continuously collected between 1st May 2020 up to now.

How often is it updated?

The dataset is updated daily with the new most popular artworks.

Who owns it (rights statement if applicable)/License:

The dataset is subject to License compliance with the terms and conditions of the agreement found at the following webpage: <https://www.deviantart.com/about/policy/api/>. DeviantArt grants Licensee a non-exclusive, non-transferable and revocable licence to its access and content. The code used to download the data will be made available.

What indicators might apply?

Here we deal mainly with time stamped data which has a clearly artistic component. Therefore, those indicators deriving from time series analysis are suitable. Artworks in DevianArt can be also sold, so indicators on economic impact fit in the analysis. If properly crossed with other datasets, the reuse of cultural assets can be addressed.

Alltheater.es

Alltheater.es is a subscription-based streaming service which offers online streaming of a library of theater plays, mainly in Spanish language.

What information is in this data?

We have access to time series extracted from Google Analytics reporting (i) the origin of the platform visitors, as well as the drop rate as they navigate the site, and (ii) the flow of users from social networks (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, etc.) and their drop rate.

We also have 4 months of the daily sales of the platform, including detailed information on the number of sold items and on the net average of the sales, among other elements.

What is the size of the data set?

The data totals 530KB.

Where does it come from?

We reached an agreement with the *Alltheater.es*' CEO and they shared directly with us some of their data.

Data type/format

The data is organized in CSV files.

Publication Date

The data covers the period between 1st January 2020 and 27th April 2020.

How often is it updated?

Automatic updates were not agreed upon: to receive a new dataset we would have to request it to *Alltheater.es*.

Who owns it (rights statement if applicable)/License:

This dataset is owned by *Alltheater.es*. At the moment cannot be made publicly available as we do not have the permission from *Alltheater.es*.

What indicators might apply?

This dataset provides the unique opportunity of tracking the growth in the online media consumption associated with the COVID-19 lockdown of spring 2020, using indicators borrowed from time-series analysis.

Facebook and Instagram

Facebook and Instagram are two of the most popular social media platforms, where huge volumes of messages and images are transmitted daily.

What information is in this data?

The data include all the messages of selected accounts, when the message was posted, the type of post (image, video, text) plus the content (link to image or video, or the text message), and different sort of interacting statistics (likes, reactions, comments, shares, video views).

What is the size of the data set?

The size of the data is 18MB compressed.

Where does it come from?

We accessed this data via CrowdTangle, a social media tracking platform that offers the possibility to search and download different sorts of content from Facebook, Instagram and Reddit. It gives access to the public content of these online social networks, as well as it is a tool implemented to follow, analyze and report online trends. Full CrowdTangle access is subject to a paywall for the general public, but it may become free for researchers if one's application is accepted, which was our case.

Data type/format

All files are in CSV format.

Publication Date

The current data set spans a time range of more than 4 years, from 1st January 2017 to 1st May 2021. This can be expanded both to older dates and to the present date.

How often is it updated?

This data set has been obtained manually, all at once, by selecting the time ranges and granularity that were suitable for us. It can eventually be accessed via API in order to regularly automatize the updates.

Who owns it (rights statement if applicable)/License:

Regarding the License, CrowdTangle grants a worldwide non-exclusive, non-transferable, freely revocable non-sublicensable license to access and use the Services (see Services [here](#)). CrowdTangle reserves all rights not expressly granted herein in the Services. CrowdTangle retains title and ownership of all rights (including copyright, trademark, patent, trade secret and all other intellectual property rights) in and to the Services.

What indicators might apply?

This data set mainly comprises time statistics of the followed accounts, therefore we can use the set of indicators related to time series analysis. If the data set is enriched with other data sets, it could eventually be explored with indicators on economic impact.

3.2. Data Collected at WLT

News Media Corpus

Intended as a generic, domain-independent content repository, the dataset represents a language-specific set of Web Sources (identified via their URLs) of major News Media outlets, e.g. *The New York Times*, *Die Welt*, *Reuters* etc.. For the inDICES use cases, the set was extended by a collection of about 50 Italian Online Media Sources which contains, for example, *la Repubblica*, *L'Unione Sarda*, and *Today*. As of September 2021 the News Media Corpus totals 1346 mirrored Web Sources across the different languages. The dataset is continuously updated through WLT's crawling architecture. The data collection process respects the Web site owner's *robots.txt* settings (a text file placed in the top directory, which is used by site administrators to restrict access to files and directories on a Web server).

The resulting dataset is an index of JSON serialized documents, following the WLT document model¹, where each document captures the textual content and metadata. The document metadata consists of both, extracted metadata and enriched metadata. In the first category fall, for example, author, published datetime, location and linked content. The enriched metadata consists of NLP tokenized sentences, extracted keywords, recognized named entities (persons, locations, organizations), polarity and sentiment.

The resulting data is made available for the project via REST APIs and the inDICES dashboard and stored persistently on the WLT server cluster. Between January 2020 and September 2021 a total of 30 million English, German, Spanish, French, Dutch and Italian documents were collected.

Figure 1: Content Distribution of gathered News media across languages between Jan 2020 and Aug 2021. The chart reflects the activation of Spanish (brown) and Italian (orange) articles as of January 2021 and April 2021, respectively.

Web Corpus / CCS Corpus

Analog to the News Media Corpus, the Web Corpus is a collection of JSON serialized documents. Content is gathered from various Web Sites outside the News domain, e.g. online magazines, domain-specific journals, business websites, online blogs etc. Analogous to the news corpus strategy, the data collection process respects the Web site owner's robots.txt settings to avoid unauthorized access. Total sources mirrored amount to around 3600, including monthly and weekly magazines, online blogs, covering sectors such as IT (Internet Technology), travel or food.

¹ A technical description can be found at https://api.webyzard.com/doc/ui/#/Document_API

Through the inDICES partners, sources from the *Cultural and Creative Sector* (CCS) have been collected and integrated into the Web Corpus (see section 3.3). Additionally a set of museums, archives and libraries based in the Netherlands has been extracted from Wikidata as part of a pilot case, and their respective Web Sites were added to the source configuration. They currently total at 2200 sources.

All documents are enriched with metadata and available through the same mechanisms as the News Media Corpus, providing a unified API-based access system. This dataset is intended for the analysis of term frequency distributions over time and across regions, term associations, average sentiment for a given time period, and for conducting impact evaluations.

Description	Count	Reach	Impact ▼	Sentiment
theartnewspaper.com museum · art · art market	1854	0.79	1465	+0.29
AR artreview.com biennale · art · artist	712	0.66	470	0
louvrefr museum · events · louvre	476	0.86	409	-0.1
museivaticani.va museums · holy see (vatican city state) ...	386	0.52	200	+0.35
beeldengeluid.nl beeld · sound · vision	320	0.59	189	+0.51
musee-orsay.fr orsay · museum · musée	202	0.78	158	+0.03
RUKS rijksmuseum.nl rijksmuseum · canvas · amsterdam	198	0.77	153	+0.33
petitpalais.paris.fr booking · dates · hardware the	134	0.89	119	+0.24
kham.at kunsthistorisches · vienna · museum	81	0.7	57	+0.53
amsterdammuseum.nl carriage · museum · amsterdam	74	0.62	46	+0.43
oslomuseum.no oslo · city · exhibition	10	0.46	5	+0.1
belvedere.at belvedere · allure · 1930s	3	0.5	2	+0.63
bundesarchiv.de	2	0.67	1	+0.5

Figure 2: An excerpt of the content from some of the added CCS sources showing the count of collected documents, reach and impact metrics and the overall associated sentiment.

Social Media Corpus

This dataset consists of a set of social media postings collected from different social networks. To gather the data, we use the official APIs provided by those networks, strictly adhering to these platform's usage restrictions and only accessing the public portion of the content.

The core experiments are run on Twitter content as a result of queries on specified terms of interest and accounts of relevance, given the limitations of other platforms such as Facebook. Additionally, a limited amount of generic Facebook and Youtube content is part of the dataset. Should the need arise for additional non-Twitter

content, the data gathering configuration will be adjusted in the coming months, in order to accurately reflect the topics of interest.

The dataset itself is an index of JSON serialized documents, where each document captures the content of one social media posting and associated metadata, including datetime, user information (user id, status, followers, thumbnail), geo location, and enriched metadata based on the processed text, i.e. keywords, named entities, sentiment. Between January 2020 and September 2021 a total of 77 million Tweets were collected (~95% of them after January 2021) and enriched across all languages, with the majority of 72 million being English tweets.

Description	Count	Reach	Impact ▼	Sentiment
openculture art · comedy · divine	291	0.9	262	+0.17
britishlibrary library · question · collection	140	1	140	+0.29
creativecommons creative commons · summit · presenter	130	0.9	117	+0.42
europe_creative europe · relations · heritage	41	0.7	29	+0.86
actforculture future · culture · campaign	38	0.6	23	+0.24
vangoghmuseum van gogh · museum · artists	20	1	20	+0.19
ubleiden year · oration · online	37	0.5	19	+0.25
rijksmuseum netherlands · collection · centre	22	0.8	18	+0.36
allard_pierson reading · amsterdam · book	30	0.4	12	+0.16
museumboerhaave leiden · boerhaave · dress	20	0.6	12	+0.25
gronarch groningen · groningen · is m	25	0.4	10	-0.01
vanabbemuseum weekend · collection presentation · art	14	0.6	8	+0.07
zeeuwsarchief	20	0.4	8	+0.17

Figure 3: Gathered Tweets from the Top CCS Twitter Sources in September 2021.

CHI Knowledge Graph - GLAM Entities (NL Pilot)

The dataset is a set of RDF (Resource Description Framework) – W3C² specifications for metadata modelling of web resources – statements that represent factual knowledge about cultural organizations of interest and associated entity-level metadata derived from Linked Open Data (LOD) sources. The initial set of Dutch entities was generated based on a SPARQL query, defining wikidata entity types and subtypes of interest, while excluding types that lead to undesired results. The main focus were Dutch GLAM organizations (museums, libraries and archives). The resulting set of ~2000 entities was provided to Dutch project partner NISV as a

² World Wide Web Consortium, see <https://www.w3.org/>

google spreadsheet for review, and extended with additional metadata, such as further associated social media accounts that are not available in the wikidata model. Afterwards the data was transformed into RDF triples and stored as part of the webLizard semantic knowledge base. In order to clearly identify and connect this new subset of entities, processes were put into place that allow for storing entities into different SPARQL graphs within one dataset.

Through an entity recognition and information extraction pipeline the new entities are associated when their surface forms, i.e. names or name variations are mentioned in document text and can be tracked for content analysis.

It is planned to further extend this set with relevant entities from other European countries.

The preservation of the original wikidata dataset is stored in a Blazegraph triple store and any customized metadata is stored in an Apache Fuseki triple store hosted by WLT, including information when they were created and with what associated provenance. Both follow predefined RDF schemas for representing and storing linked data. The triple store is synchronized with a distributed Elasticsearch index for faster querying and metadata retrieval.

Accessibility and Integration into the Open Observatory

The documents in the News Media, the Web and the Social Media corpora are accessible to project partners via REST APIs where access is granted via API key upon request, and through the inDICES dashboard that is part of the Open Observatory, with the option to generate PDF reports and download partial datasets as CSV. Embeddable visualizations, such as a tag cloud, a keyword graph and a geographic map, computed from the WLT collected datasets are integrated into the Participatory Space, both to contextualize user interactions, and as part of the Dashboard Lite to quickly visualize predefined topics and areas of interest for inDICES target audiences and stakeholders. The collected datasets themselves are only accessible as part of the inDICES project for authenticated users / client applications.

For collected data from the Web and social networks we respect all guidelines and limits of the content owners – i.e., the social network API terms and conditions as well as the instructions published via the robots.txt file for Web pages. A pointer back to the original content and the original URL is stored in the database and is always shown in conjunction with the search results, to both guarantee credit to the content owner and refer to the original source.

The gathered datasets provide a comprehensive overview of the current media landscape, encompassing world news as well as the specific debates and

stakeholder communication highly relevant to the cultural sector - via institutional websites, magazines, blogs and social media channels, that are collected and processed in close to real-time. With it the latest trends and rising topics can be discovered and taken into account for planning dissemination strategies, optimizing public outreach activities and connecting with key audiences. Additional data metrics that are computed and offered through interactive components of the *Visual Analytics Dashboard* make it easy for the observer to assess frequency of content, impact of a document by taking the reach of the data source into consideration, or the sentiment associated with the coverage of a certain topic. Through the extraction of top keywords and associations the user can easily extend or restrict the search and change the topic of investigation, being guided by arising content connections. Possible use cases include tracking a single institutions coverage and perception in comparison to competitors, detecting promising strategies that are pursued by acknowledged institutions in the field or geographic area, or following the evolution of the public discussion on topics of interest, e.g. EU Copyright Directive, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or the digitization of cultural assets.

Figure 4: A comparison of the top web sources covering “contemporary art”. Top: Document Frequency from May to September 2021. Middle: Relation Tracker showing top associated person entities (colors represent sentiment). Right: GeoMap, Tag Cloud and Keyword Graph.

3.3 Case studies lists and Trend indicators

In order to set and implement the data analysis process on CHIs' social networks users' behavior, with a special focus on the Covid19 wave of forced digitization, WP1 partners prepared a set of lists of accounts whose past and current activity we aim to monitor. WP1, to M21, built a set of case-studies, made by lists of Facebook and Instagram accounts, per macro-sectoral areas of cultural and creative institutions. The sectors' case studies that have been outlined and analysed to M21 are (see D1.4 section 3 for further details regarding the criteria of selection of CHIs per each list):

- European National Libraries sector
- European Archives Institutes sector
- Most Visited European Museums
- Museums that employ the Virtual Tour tool on a global scale

The additional lists that have been realized, and that WP1 planned to analyze with the same research objectives, from M22 to M24, are:

- European Theatres
- European Archeological sites
- Fashion GLAMS
- a case study list regarding the macro-sector of the Audiovisual, which criteria have to be collectively defined via inDICES internal Hypothesis Assembly.

The lists of websites, aimed at being integrated within the Visual Analytics Dashboard, that have been realized and still need to be perfected, regards:

- Movie festivals
- Contemporary art and Art Market
- Performance/Theatre/Critics
- GLAM list
- wikidata GLAMs
- Lit-journals/blogs (on cultural content)
- Open Access Journals (on cultural content)

The content of the lists that have been finalized to M21 can be found in the Annex I to this deliverable.

Per each list, respectively CCS, WP1 partners defined "trend indicators" – collections of specific lemmas – to be investigated and related topics defined and analyzed via the Visual Analytics Dashboard, with the goal to perform trend and impact analysis for various CCS through web content and social media posts, shedding light on socio-cultural trends.

4. Usefulness and limitations

One of the goals of inDICES is to offer the tools to help researchers, CCIs, and policy-makers and decision-makers track policies and cultural trends over the long-term. To achieve this we need to approach the cultural ecosystem from different viewpoints and from different scales: from the micro (individuals), meso (CCIs, organizations, etc.), to macro (transnational, EU-wide, worldwide). An alternative classification of cultural dynamics is through the mode of production: from Culture 1.0, based on patronage, to Culture 2.0, typical of the cultural and creative industries, and to Culture 3.0, characteristic of open platforms [P.L. Sacco, *Culture 3.0: A new perspective for the EU 2014-2020 structural funds programming*. OMC Working Group on Cultural and Creative Industries (2011)]. The collected data discussed in Section 3 aims to offer a representative coverage of these types and modes present on the web.

The data collected, described in this deliverable, aim at achieving this goal. We envision their use by a wide audience of users (citizens, non-profit organizations, researchers, policy makers) interested in the possible implications of digital platforms on cultural production. In particular, the dissemination targets identified by WP4 being policy makers, practitioners and researchers, we can highlight here three different modes of use that could be the most common.

The first, and most immediate, concerns the direct consultation of research outputs in the form of figures, tables, statistics and research reports, suitably presented and organized to make them accessible, understandable and usable also by non-technical audiences, while at the same time providing materials that are of interest for more technically and research-oriented users. The user pool would include policy makers aiming at defining or improving policies on active participation via social platforms and practitioners (or artists) willing to understand the value of developing new digital strategies/tools or practices of bottom-up/collective co-creation. In this way, users have immediate access to the full array of complex information captured by the data, and can thus analyze and identify the trends regarding the impact of digital platforms and tools on the behavior of online users and the new forms of cultural production that the latter make possible in the virtual space of the Internet. The second is the integration into an Observatory Platform and an Interactive Dashboard that allows you to build one's own specific research question to which attempt to answer or to set the free parameters of analysis in such a way as to intercept trends or converging sectors that, at first, have not been deeply analyzed during inDICES. Finally, a last mode concerns the direct access to raw data, in this way the most advanced users will be able to create new autonomous ways of using data, leaving open future opportunities not explored at the time of the inDICES conclusion.

The possible uses of the collected data on inDICES are many: they range from the primary need to understand cultural trends, to the implementation of cultural policies aimed at specific sectors such as museums or contemporary art exhibitions, up to tiny niche sectors, such as, for example, the construction of film scenes using eco-sustainable paper materials. These heterogeneous modalities show how there is no single way to use the data and the analysis and tools provided by inDICES, but how in general a descriptive, exploratory and explanatory use is what we expect users to adopt. This is also dictated by the fact that inDICES will be providing one of the first tools of this kind in the cultural sector, while others exist for more consolidated sectors from this point of view, such as the economic or environmental sectors. Therefore, we expect a use similar to what has been done in the past within the more consolidated economic and social sectors. Finally, the workshops conducted so far have reinforced this point of view by showing how the same participants and stakeholders have emphasized and wished for a use that basically reflects the ideas behind the production of the research output of inDICES, that is, making use of appropriate computational tools to better understand the less obvious dimensions and aspects of the changes that the digital large-scale production and participation dynamics that characterizes the Culture 3.0 regime is bringing about in the cultural field.

To serve this wide variety of users and use cases, we have gathered (and will continue to gather up to M36, that will be discussed in D1.5 and D1.6) a multiplicity of datasets useful to understand how cultural production spreads in the digital realm, give hints on the user behavior on these cultural platforms—which is something that has not systematically researched so far—, as well as to pave the way for future theoretical and applied research. Moreover, they are also helpful in that they can be employed as use cases to inspire future users of the Observatory Platform.

During these months spent in acquiring and analyzing data, we have found a number of obstacles. In some cases, we took steps to overcome them, but in other cases the very nature of the dataset necessarily limits its usability in terms of **quality**, **reliability** and **accessibility**.

The first dataset we got access to were already-available on-line sources and relevant reports on the CHI digitalization status and socio-economic impact across the EU (see D1.3). Although these resources can be useful so far for a wide range of researchers and practitioners (see D1.3), these datasets were created through a standard process of direct consultation with institutions through surveys, which revealed two limitations: first, that the number of participating institutions was in sharp decline after the first wave; second, that they lacked accurate data regarding the interaction between the digitized objects of their work and the web ecosystem. Finally, a final problem was inherent in the granularity of the data collected, which, of

necessity, could not be temporally unpacked into micro periods (hours or days) nor for types of users or audience (citizens or the private).

Conversely, the datasets described in this deliverable attempt at capturing the complex nature of the global cultural digitalization process, that can be instead tracked in quasi-real time using the web-based methodologies. This alternative solution comes however with particular limitations, specific of each dataset:

Dataset	Limitations	Solution Implemented
Wikipedia	Huge data dimensionality.	We limited our data collection to one-shot download, not automatically updated.
IMDb	Non transferable licence.	We plan to share the data collection code
Tiktok	Technical limitation in analyzing visual content. Video data loss due to deletion by users.	Analysis focused on the networks of interaction between users and communities.
DeviantArt	Limited number of queries in the API. Non transferable licence.	Data collection limited to the top lists. We plan to share the data collection code.
Alltheater.es	Short period of collection. Sensitive economical data from a small company.	Use limited to case study analysis, that must be mindful of providing only relative trends and not absolute values.
Social media data (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter)	Content can contain personal data protected by the GDPR, and the platform's terms of use state that content cannot be openly shared as a bulk dataset.	We analyze the data in aggregated form via Crowdtangle and the Visual Analytics Dashboard. We offer authenticated access to stakeholders through the inDICES Visual Analytic Dashboard
News Media data	The publishing sites hold the copyright of the articles, which therefore cannot be made available publicly.	We offer limited access to the stakeholders through our Visual Analytic Dashboard

4.1 Use cases

We offer some use cases to illustrate how the datasets gathered so far could be employed and how they could target different profiles.

- **Independent Researcher.**
Impact areas: Culture 3.0, Cultural production, Digital commons, Internet studies
Dataset: Wikipedia

An independent researcher is studying the role of a cultural elite in the digital knowledge systems. The hypothesis to test is whether or not in horizontal, open digital platforms, such as Wikipedia, there is a set of users that become an elite of producers driving the peer-to-peer production process. There, he/she does not have neither the proper dataset nor the metrics to identify if there is an elite and quantify their influence on the other users and the process of knowledge production

With the Wikipedia dataset and some indicators developed in D1.1, such as Gini index about content production and the topological position of the actors in the network of content production, these questions can be addressed.

- **Success of a cultural campaign**

Impact areas: Social/Public marketing, public communication

Dataset: Twitter, Facebook

Cultural organizations seek to maximize the impact of a marketing campaign. Without data, it is difficult to know when it is the right moment to start the advertising of a public event and how to track the success of the digital campaign.

Looking at the online activity of other cultural institutions/organizations, we can learn and extract information of different patterns based on hit economy metrics (attention, time-series of total interaction, etc.) and propose and track different strategies of marketing gamification (e.g., hashtag races).

- **Artists' coefficient of a self-employed artist**

Impact areas: management, contemporary art, galleries

Dataset: Web Corpus

The artistic coefficient is used to calculate the market value of an artwork. It is a widespread practice in art galleries that want to include an artwork in a catalog. This coefficient, however, is a subjective measure based on the criteria of the gallerist and the market tendencies.

A problem that many self-employed artists face is the unavailability of calculating their own artist coefficient, especially for those working in the digital realm. They cannot trace their digital impact, e.g., in news and blogs on contemporary art and in social networks. The VAD offers a tool to trace these trends and thus help the artist better redefine the price of his/her artworks by suitably combining this source of information with more established ones such as those related to artistic reputation (e.g. as tracked by artifacts.net).

- **Content Creator / Social Media Editor for a Cultural Institution**

Impact areas: User Engagement, Marketing

Dataset: News Media Corpus / Web Corpus / Social Media Corpus

As a content creator or social media editor of my institution, I want to increase the reach and impact of my site - in general and in terms of specific articles - through content optimization. I can use visual widgets to illustrate ongoing campaigns and detect trending topics that I can then use to refine my strategy or incorporate into actual posts. With the help of sentiment analysis I can avoid topics with a negative connotation and focus on contributions to solution-based, valuable discussions that increase my institution's reach and improve public perception. I can further restrict my search to similar institutions in the field to see which topics or services they currently promote.

- **CHI Professional with Interest in Digitalization**

Impact areas: Digitalization, Business Intelligence

Dataset: News Media Corpus / Web Corpus utilizing CHI Knowledge Graph

As a CHI professional that is interested in digital transformation, I need to identify high-impact topics surrounding digitalization that can improve my institution's daily work. The interactive inDICES dashboard helps me to scout the latest technology trends, learn about related topics and organizations in my field, and identify leading experts to reach out to in order to learn about best practice and synergies or even establish a formal collaboration.

5. Data organizational scheme

As discussed in the deliverable D1.1 and D1.3, users will be provided access to the various datasets and content resources provided by inDICES partner on CHI digitization via the inDICES Repository and the Open Observatory Platform. This would require the integration of a variety of sources and formats as well as developing effective information architecture.

The Open Observatory Platform is distributed mainly in two independent places: The customized Decidim application for InDICES and the WLT Visual Analytics Dashboard. These two applications use different technologies and have different purposes:

Visual Analytics Dashboard

The Visual Analytics Dashboard is dedicated to ingest massive amounts of data and provides a frontend for analyzing it. Only a subset of the Open Observatory users, with the right permissions, has the ability to access the dashboard, however, the application also provides an API for InDICES to automatically integrate some of the widgets into the main platform, without requiring any special user privileges. For this purpose, custom tools have been developed on top of Decidim to integrate it with the Visual Analytics Dashboard. This includes, for instance, automatic analysis of posts uploaded in the platform users and relate them to external or internal content.

Decidim

Decidim is the public face of the project and handles all primary user interactions. It effectively acts as a social network providing several spaces with features like comments, creating posts, sharing with others, etc. It provides a framework for allowing users to insert content into the platform and a place to develop interactive applications. One of these applications will be a catalog of the different data sources, the “Data repository”, organized according to a structured criteria, with links to papers or any other relevant information. In some cases it will also allow users to download the datasets or a processed subset of them for external analysis. However, it will not be a dynamic source of datasets, as any content here needs to be curated and validated by a proper administrator to ensure the quality of the results.

Figure 5. Integration flow with the two platforms composing the Open Observatory

Thus far WP4 has hosted several assemblies to begin to create the information architecture within which the ‘Data repository’ would fit as well as incorporated it within WP4’s user experience research and strategy development. To develop the platform WP4 engaged in user experience research creating, personas, user stories, user journeys, and facilitated sessions for partners to co-create and experiment with use cases. Much of the work done is detailed in D4.1 and D5.6.

Specifically concerning the data repository, several use case exercises were conducted amongst partners to test how they saw the data generated by FBK fitting into the needs of CHI practitioners and researchers. Ultimately, the data generated by the repository is not for a general audience but more towards a technical, research audience. Therefore, within the platform interface the data repository within the overarching architecture will be most easily accessible for those working within academic or technical knowledge oriented fields.

Another relevant application developed on top of Decidim, is the “self assessment tool” which will allow users to evaluate their own processes’ status of digitalization. The self-assessment bench-marking tool will allow CHI institutions to “measure” where they find themselves on the route to Digital Transformation and co-creative user-engagement. The SAT may also provide a pathway to those interested in the data observatory, because it may offer the data observatory as part of a series of recommendations depending on the user’s input of their needs.

Finally, the access to the Visualization Dashboard will be controlled by Decidim, assigning different roles to certain users and allowing them to seamlessly change between the two underlying technologies.

In summary, the Visual Analytics Dashboard will handle large amounts of data (ie: “big data”) returning digested results and visualizations and can be used by individual contributors to generate reports and curated datasets to be made available in the Data repository.

ANNEX I: Case study lists

List Name - CCS	Name	Website
National Libraries	The Vatican Library	https://www.vaticanlibrary.va/
National Libraries	National Library of Spain	http://www.bne.es/es/Inicio/index.html
National Libraries	National Library of Portugal	http://www.bnportugal.gov.pt
National Libraries	National Library of the Republic of Moldova	http://www.bnrm.md/
National Libraries	National Library of Romania	http://www.bibnat.ro/
National Libraries	The Central National Library of Florence	https://www.bncf.firenze.sbn.it/
National Libraries	The Central National Library of Rome	http://www.bnrcrm.beniculturali.it/
National Libraries	National Library of Albania	https://www.bksh.al/
National Libraries	National Library of Poland	https://www.bn.org.pl/
National Libraries	National Library of France	https://www.bnf.fr/fr
National Libraries	National Library of Luxembourg	https://bnl.public.lu/fr.html
National Libraries	The National Library of Malta	https://www.cenl.org/library/malta-libraries-the-national-library-of-malta/
National Libraries	British Library	https://www.bl.uk/
National Libraries	National Library of Denmark	https://www.kb.dk/
National Libraries	German National Library	https://www.dnb.de/DE/Home/home_node.html
National Libraries	National Library of Estonia	https://www.nlib.ee/
National Libraries	The National Library of Finland	https://www.kansalliskirjasto.fi/fi
National Libraries	Royal Library of the Netherlands	https://www.kb.nl/

National Libraries	Royal Library of Belgium	https://www.kbr.be/en/
National Libraries	National Library of Sweden	https://www.kb.se/
National Libraries	National University Library of Iceland	https://landsbokasafn.is/
National Libraries	National Library of Latvia	https://www.lnb.lv/
National Libraries	National Library of Ireland	https://www.cenl.org/library/national-library-of-ireland/
National Libraries	National Library of Liechtenstein	https://www.landesbibliothek.li/
National Libraries	Martynas Mazvydas National Library of Lithuania	https://www.lnb.lt/
National Libraries	National Library of Azerbaijan	http://anl.az/new/
National Libraries	National Library of Turkey	http://www.millikutuphane.gov.tr/
National Libraries	National Library of Montenegro	https://www.nb-cg.me/
National Libraries	National and University Library in Zagreb	https://www.nsk.hr/
National Libraries	National and University Library of Bosnia and Herzegovina	https://www.cenl.org/library/nacionalna-i-univerzitetska-biblioteka/
National Libraries	National and University Library St. Kliment Ohridski	http://nubsk.edu.mk/
National Libraries	National and University Library of Slovenia	https://www.nuk.uni-lj.si/
National Libraries	National Library of the Czech Republic	https://www.nkp.cz/
National Libraries	National Library of Norway	https://www.nb.no/
National Libraries	National Library of Hungary	http://www.oszk.hu/
National Libraries	National Library of Austria	https://www.onb.ac.at/

National Libraries	Swiss National Library	https://www.nb.admin.ch/snl/de/home.html
National Libraries	Slovak National Library	https://www.snk.sk/en/
National Libraries	National Library of Greece	https://www.nlg.gr/
National Libraries	Cyprus Library	http://www.cypruslibrary.gov.cy/moec/cl/cl.nsf/DMLindex_gr/DMLindex_gr?opendocument
National Libraries	National Library of Serbia	https://www.nb.rs/
National Libraries	St. St. Cyril and Methodius National Library	http://nationallibrary.bg/wp/
National Libraries	V. Vernadsky National Library of Ukraine	http://www.nbu.gov.ua/
National Libraries	Boris Yeltsin Presidential Library	https://www.prlib.ru/
National Libraries	Russian State Library	https://www.rsl.ru/
National Libraries	National Library of Russia	http://nlr.ru/
Archives	BBC Archives	https://www.bbc.co.uk/archive
Archives	Austrian State Archives	https://www.statearchives.gv.at/
Archives	Rijksarchief	http://www.arch.be/index.php?!=nl
Archives	Cinemathek (Royal Film Archive of Belgium)	http://www.cinematheque.be/
Archives	The Archives of Bulgaria	http://www.arhiv.hr/hr-hr/
Archives	Croatian State Archives	http://www.arhiv.hr/hr-hr/
Archives	Národní filmový archiv	https://nfa.cz/
Archives	the Danish National Archives	https://www.sa.dk/en/
Archives	National Archives of Estonia	https://www.ra.ee/
Archives	National Archives of Finland	https://arkisto.fi/
Archives	INA	https://www.ina.fr/

Archives	Archives nationales	https://www.archives-nationales.culture.gouv.fr/en/web/guest/home
Archives	Das Bundesarchiv	https://www.bundesarchiv.de/DE/Navigation/Home/home.html
Archives	Bauhaus Archive	https://www.bauhaus.de/en/
Archives	Greek Film Archive	http://www.tainiothiki.gr/en/
Archives	National Archives of Hungary	https://mnl.gov.hu/angol
Archives	RTE archives	https://www.rte.ie/archives
Archives	National Archives	https://www.nationalarchives.ie/
Archives	Central Archives of the State	https://www.acs.beniculturali.it/
Archives	Luce	https://www.archivioluce.com/
Archives	National Archives of Latvia	https://www.arhivi.gov.lv/
Archives	Lithuanian State Archive	http://www.archyvai.lt/en/news.html
Archives	Lithuanian State Modern Archives	http://www.archyvai.lt/lt/lvna_naujienos.html
Archives	National Archives Luxembourg	https://anlux.public.lu/fr.html
Archives	National Archives of Malta	https://nationalarchives.gov.mt/en/Pages/default.aspx
Archives	Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision	https://www.beeldengeluid.nl/
Archives	National Archives	https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/
Archives	National Archives of Norway	https://www.arkivverket.no/en
Archives	Filmoteka Narodowa - Instytut Audiowizualny	http://www.fn.org.pl/en.html
Archives	Narodowe Archiwum Cyfrowe	https://nac.gov.pl/
Archives	Arhivele Nationale ale	http://arhivelenationale.ro/site/

	Romaniei	
Archives	Historical archives Ljubljana	http://www.zal-lj.si/
Archives	Archivos Estatales	http://pares.culturaydeporte.gob.es/inicio.html
Archives	Archivo Lafuente	https://www.archivolafuente.com/
Archives	Riksarkivet Sverige	https://riksarkivet.se/startpage
Archives	Swiss Film Archive	https://www.cinematheque.ch/e/
Archives	Schweizerisches Bundesarchiv	https://www.bar.admin.ch/bar/en/home.html
Fashion	CatwalkPictures	https://www.catwalkpictures.com/index,en.html
Fashion	Fashion Museum of Hasselt	https://www.modemuseumhasselt.be/
Fashion	MoMu Fashion Museum of Antwerp	https://www.momu.be/it/visitor-information
Fashion	Shoes Or No Shoes?	https://www.shoesornoshoes.com/
Fashion	Fashion & Lace Museum	https://www.fashionandlacemuseum.brussels/fr/
Fashion	Fashion Museum	https://www.palaisgalliera.paris.fr/
Fashion	Yves Saint Laurent Museum	https://museeyslparis.com/
Fashion	City of Lace and Fashion	https://www.cite-dentelle.fr/en/
Fashion	The Shoe Museum of Villa Foscari Rossi	https://www.museodellacalzatura.it/
Fashion	Gianfranco Ferré Foundation	https://www.fondazionegianfrancoferre.com/home/intro.php
Fashion	FILA Foundation Museum	https://www.fondazionefila.com/en/
Fashion	Cerratelli Foundation	http://fondazionecerratelli.it/
Fashion	International Talent Support	https://www.itsweb.org/jsp/en/index/index.jsp
Fashion	Armani/Silos	https://www.armanisilos.com
Fashion	Prato Textile Musuem	https://www.museodeltessuto.it/

Fashion	Museo Salvatore Ferragamo	https://www.ferragamo.com/museo/it
Fashion	Modemuze	https://www.modemuze.nl/
Fashion	Textile Museum	https://textielmuseum.nl/en/
Fashion	Textile Research Centre	https://www.trc-leiden.nl/trc/index.php/en/
Fashion	Central Museum of Textiles in Łódź	https://cmwl.pl/public/
Fashion	Museum of Design and Fashion	http://www.mude.pt/
Fashion	Costume Museum	https://www.culturaydeporte.gob.es/mtraje/inicio.html
Fashion	Cristóbal Balenciaga Museum	https://www.cristobalbalenciagamuseoa.com
Fashion	Balenciaga Museum	https://www.cristobalbalenciagamuseoa.com/en/
Fashion	Fashion Museum Bath	https://www.fashionmuseum.co.uk/
Fashion	Fashion and Textile Museum	https://www.ftmlondon.org/
Fashion	Westminster Menswear Archive	https://www.mensweararchive.com/
Fashion	Zegna Foundation	http://www.fondazionezegna.org/
Fashion	Yorkshire Fashion Archive	https://ahc.leeds.ac.uk/homepage/254/yorkshire_fashion_archive
Fashion	Archivio Pucci	https://pucci-dev.promemoriagroup.com/#/
Fashion	Missoni Archive	http://www.archiviomissoni.org/
National Theaters	National Theater of Albania	http://www.teatrikombetar.gov.al/
National Theaters	National Theater of Linz	http://www.landestheater-linz.at/
National Theaters	The National Theater - Graz Opera	http://www.schauspielhaus-graz.com/
National Theaters	Liege Theatre	https://theatredeliege.be

National Theaters	Theatre Laboratory Sfumato	http://sfumato.info/
National Theaters	Theater and Music Center Kardjali	http://www.dktdimov.com/
National Theaters	Croatian National Theater	https://www.hnk.hr/hr/raspored/
National Theaters	National Theater Prague	http://www.narodni-divadlo.cz/
National Theaters	Prague City Theatres	http://www.mestskadivadlaprazska.cz/
National Theaters	Cyprus Theater Organization	https://www.thoc.org.cy/index/el
National Theaters	Estonian Drama Theater	https://www.draamateater.ee
National Theaters	Finish National Theater	https://kansallisteatteri.fi
National Theaters	The manufacture	http://www.theatre-manufacture.fr/
National Theaters	Odeon Theater	https://www.theatre-odeon.eu/fr#1
National Theaters	Kote Marjanishvili State Drama Theatre	http://www.marjanishvili.com/
National Theaters	Meskhishvili Professional State Drama theatre	http://meskhishviliitheatre.ge/index.html
National Theaters	Deutsches Theater Berlin	http://www.deutschestheater.de/
National Theaters	Heidelberg Theater and Orchestra	http://www.theaterheidelberg.de/
National Theaters	National Theatre of Northern Grece	http://www.ntng.gr/
National Theaters	The Magyar Theater	http://www.pestimagyarszinhaz.hu/
National Theaters	Weöres Sándor Theatre	http://wssz.hu
National Theaters	Due theater foundation	http://www.teatrodue.org/
National Theaters	Koreja Theatre	http://www.teatrokoreja.it/
National Theaters	Theater of Rome	http://www.teatrodiroma.net
National Theaters	New Theater Institute of Latvia	http://theatre.lv

National Theaters	Lithuanian National Drama Theater	https://www.teatras.lt/lt
National Theaters	The theaters of Luxembourg city	http://www.lestheatres.lu/
National Theaters	The Escher Theater	https://theatre.esch.lu
National Theaters	Malta Theater	http://www.teatrumalta.org.mt/
National Theaters	The Norwegian Theater	http://www.detnorsketeatret.no/
National Theaters	JK Opole Theater	https://teatropole.pl
National Theaters	Helena Modrzejewska National Stary Theatre	http://stary.pl/en/
National Theaters	National Theater São João	http://www.tnsj.pt/
National Theaters	National Theatre D. Maria II	http://www.tndm.pt/pt
National Theaters	Timisoara National Theater	http://www.tntimisoara.com/
National Theaters	Alexandra Davilu Theater	http://www.teatruldavila.ro/
National Theaters	National Theatre in Belgrade	https://www.narodnopozeriste.rs/
National Theaters	Yugoslav Drama Theatre	http://www.jdp.rs/
National Theaters	Slovak National Drama Theater	http://www.snd.sk/en
National Theaters	Divadlo Jana Palarika	https://djp.sk/
National Theaters	Prešeren Theater	https://pgk.si
National Theaters	Slovene National Theater Nova Gorica	http://www.sng-ng.si/
National Theaters	Backa Theatre	https://stadsteatern.goteborg.se
National Theaters	The theater	http://www.toneelmakerij.nl/
National Theaters	Dakh Theater - Centre of Contemporary Arts	http://dakh.com.ua/en/
National Theaters	Kiev Academic Young Theater	https://molodyytheatre.com/

National Theaters	Belarus Free Theater	https://www.belarusfreetheatre.com
Archeological Sites	Colosseum's archaeological park	https://parcocolosseo.it/
Archeological Sites	Stonehenge	https://www.english-heritage.org.uk/stonehenge
Archeological Sites	Pont du Gard	https://www.pontdugard.fr/
Archeological Sites	The Roman baths of Bath	https://www.romanbaths.co.uk/
Archeological Sites	Brú na Bóinne - passage tombs of Newgrange, Knowth and Dowth	https://heritageireland.ie/places-to-visit/bru-na-boinne-visitor-centre-newgrange-and-knowth/
Archeological Sites	Archaeological Park Valley of the Temples in Agrigentum	https://www.parcovalledeitempli.it/en/
Archeological Sites	Archaeological site of Delphi	https://delphi.culture.gr/
Archeological Sites	Skellig Michael	https://heritageireland.ie/places-to-visit/skellig-michael/
Archeological Sites	Kernavės archeologinė vietovė	https://www.kernave.lt/en/
Archeological Sites	Roman city of Carnuntum	https://www.carnuntum.at/de/roemerstadt-carnuntum
Archeological Sites	European Archaeological Park at Bliesbruck-Reinheim	http://www.archeo57.com/
Archeological Sites	Côa Valley museum and archaeological park	https://arte-coa.pt/en/
Archeological Sites	Empúries	http://www.macempuries.cat/ca/
Archeological Sites	Pompeii archaeological park	http://pompeisites.org/
Archeological Sites	Helfštýn castle	https://helfstyn.cz/
Archeological Sites	Roman Theatre & Museum of Orange	https://www.theatre-antique.com/en/home
Archeological Sites	Mines of Spiennes	https://en.silexs.mons.be/

GLAM LIST	Academia Argentina de Letras	http://aal.edu.ar
GLAM LIST	Archivo General de la Nación Argentina	http://www.agnargentina.gob.ar
GLAM LIST	Archivo Histórico de la Provincia de Buenos Aires	https://www.amigoslevene.com
GLAM LIST	Archivo Histórico de San Luis	http://www.archivohistorico.sanluis.gov.ar
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Feminaria	http://www.tierra-violeta.com.ar
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Nacional de Maestros	http://www.bnm.me.gov.ar
GLAM LIST	Museo Casa Rosada	https://www.casarosada.gob.ar/la-casa-rosada/museo
GLAM LIST	Museo Nacional de Bellas Artes	https://www.bellasartes.gob.ar
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Nacional Aruba	http://www.bibliotecanacional.aw
GLAM LIST	ABC Open Archives	http://www.abc.net.au/archives/openarchives.htm
GLAM LIST	Australian National Maritime Museum	http://www.anmm.gov.au
GLAM LIST	Australian National University	http://www.anu.edu.au
GLAM LIST	Australian War Memorial	http://www.awm.gov.au
GLAM LIST	Blue Mountains Library (Local Studies)	https://library.bmcc.nsw.gov.au
GLAM LIST	Eyre Pensinsula Railway Preservation Society	http://www.eprps.org.au
GLAM LIST	Libraries Tasmania	https://libraries.tas.gov.au
GLAM LIST	Museum of Applied Arts and Sciences	http://maas.museum/powerhouse-museum
GLAM LIST	Museums Victoria	https://museumsvictoria.com.au

GLAM LIST	National Library of Australia	https://www.nla.gov.au
GLAM LIST	National Museum of Australia	https://www.nma.gov.au
GLAM LIST	Northern Territory Library	https://ntl.nt.gov.au
GLAM LIST	Queensland State Archives	https://www.qld.gov.au/recreation/arts/heritage/archives
GLAM LIST	Queensland University of Technology	https://www.qut.edu.au
GLAM LIST	Royal Australian Historical Society	http://www.rahs.org.au
GLAM LIST	State Library of New South Wales	http://www.sl.nsw.gov.au
GLAM LIST	State Library of Queensland	http://www.slq.qld.gov.au
GLAM LIST	State Library Victoria	http://www.slv.vic.gov.au
GLAM LIST	Swinburne University of Technology Library	https://www.swinburne.edu.au/library
GLAM LIST	Tasmanian Archive and Heritage Office	https://www.libraries.tas.gov.au
GLAM LIST	Trove Digital Library	https://trove.nla.gov.au
GLAM LIST	University of Melbourne (Melbourne History Workshop)	http://www.unimelb.edu.au
GLAM LIST	University of Tasmania (Library Open Repository)	http://www.utas.edu.au
GLAM LIST	Akademie der bildenden Künste Wien	http://www.akbild.ac.at
GLAM LIST	Belvedere	https://www.belvedere.at
GLAM LIST	Herbarium, Karl-Franzens-Universität Graz	https://botanik.uni-graz.at
GLAM LIST	Institut für Botanik, Universität Wien	http://herbarium.univie.ac.at

GLAM LIST	Österreichische Nationalbibliothek	https://www.onb.ac.at
GLAM LIST	Vorarlberger Landesbibliothek	http://www.vorarlberg.gv.at
GLAM LIST	Wien Museum	https://www.wienmuseum.at
GLAM LIST	Wienbibliothek im Rathaus	https://www.wienbibliothek.at
GLAM LIST	FelixArchief	http://www.felixarchief.be
GLAM LIST	Fotomuseum (FOMU) Antwerp	https://fomu.be
GLAM LIST	Groeningemuseum	https://www.visitbruges.be/nl/groeningemuseum
GLAM LIST	Horta Museum	http://www.hortamuseum.be
GLAM LIST	Industriemuseum	https://www.industriemuseum.be
GLAM LIST	Jakob Smitsmuseum	https://www.jakobsmits.be
GLAM LIST	King Baudouin Foundation	https://www.kbs-frb.be
GLAM LIST	Koninklijke Bibliotheek van België	https://www.kbr.be
GLAM LIST	Letterenhuis	https://www.letterenhuis.be
GLAM LIST	Liberas (Het Liberaal Archief)	http://www.liberas.eu
GLAM LIST	MoMu - Fashion Museum Antwerp	https://www.momu.be
GLAM LIST	Mu.ZEE	https://www.muzee.be
GLAM LIST	Museum Plantin-Moretus	https://www.museumplantinmoretus.be
GLAM LIST	Museum voor Schone Kunsten Gent (MSK)	https://www.mskgent.be
GLAM LIST	Plantentuin Meise	https://www.plantentuinmeise.be
GLAM LIST	Prentenkabinet, Universiteit Antwerpen	https://www.uantwerpen.be

GLAM LIST	Royal Museum of Fine Arts Antwerp	https://www.kmska.be
GLAM LIST	Universiteitsbibliotheek Gent	https://lib.ugent.be
GLAM LIST	Vlaams Architectuurinstituut	https://www.vai.be/
GLAM LIST	Arquivo Nacional	http://www.arquivonacional.gov.br
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Brasileira Guita e José Mindlin	https://www.bbm.usp.br
GLAM LIST	Museu da Imigração, São Paulo	http://museudaimigracao.org.br
GLAM LIST	Museu de Anatomia Veterinária da Faculdade de Medicina Veterinária e Zootecnia da USP	http://mav.fmvz.usp.br
GLAM LIST	Museu de Zoologia da Universidade de São Paulo	http://www.mz.usp.br
GLAM LIST	Museu do Homem do Nordeste	http://www.fundaj.gov.br
GLAM LIST	Museu Paulista	http://www.mp.usp.br
GLAM LIST	Musica Brasilis	http://musicabrasilis.org.br
GLAM LIST	Senado Federal do Brasil	http://www.senado.leg.br
GLAM LIST	NALIS Foundation	http://www.nalis.bg
GLAM LIST	Държавна агенция „Архиви (Bulgarian Archives State Agency)	https://www.archives.government.bg
GLAM LIST	Национална библиотека „Св. св. Кирил и Методий“ (SS. Cyril and Methodius National Library)	http://www.nationallibrary.bg
GLAM LIST	Регионална библиотека "Пенчо Славейков" (Pencho Slaveykov Regional Library)	http://www.libvar.bg

GLAM LIST	Регионална библиотека "Любен Каравелов" (Luben Karavelov Regional Library)	https://www.libruse.bg
GLAM LIST	Централна библиотека на БАН (Central Library of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences)	http://cl.bas.bg
GLAM LIST	Doual'art	http://doualart.org
GLAM LIST	Archives of Ontario	http://www.archives.gov.on.ca
GLAM LIST	Archives of the Law Society of Ontario	https://lso.ca
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque et Archives nationales du Québec (BAnQ)	https://www.banq.qc.ca/accueil
GLAM LIST	Canada Agriculture and Food Museum	https://ingeniumcanada.org/cafm
GLAM LIST	Canada Aviation and Space Museum	https://ingeniumcanada.org/casm
GLAM LIST	Canada Science and Technology Museum	https://ingeniumcanada.org/cstm
GLAM LIST	Cloyne Pioneer Museum and Archives	http://pioneer.mazinaw.on.ca
GLAM LIST	Congregation of Sisters of St. Joseph in Canada	http://www.csjcanada.org
GLAM LIST	Deseronto Archives	https://deserontoarchives.ca
GLAM LIST	Dundas Museum & Archives	http://www.dundasmuseum.ca
GLAM LIST	Galt Museum & Archives	https://www.galtmuseum.com
GLAM LIST	Halifax Municipal Archives	https://www.halifax.ca/about-halifax/municipal-archives
GLAM LIST	Hamilton Public Library	http://www.hpl.ca/local-history
GLAM LIST	Huron County Museum & Historic Gaol	http://huroncounty.ca/museum

GLAM LIST	Library and Archives Canada	http://www.bac-lac.gc.ca
GLAM LIST	Musée McCord	http://www.musee-mccord.gc.ca
GLAM LIST	Nova Scotia Archives	https://archives.novascotia.ca
GLAM LIST	Provincial Archives of Alberta	http://culture.alberta.ca/paa
GLAM LIST	UBC Library Digitization Centre	https://www.ubc.ca
GLAM LIST	University of Victoria Libraries	http://www.uvic.ca/library
GLAM LIST	Vancouver Public Library	http://www.vpl.ca
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Nacional de Chile	http://www.bibliotecanacional.cl
GLAM LIST	Memoria Chilena	http://www.memoriachilena.cl
GLAM LIST	Museo de la Memoria y los Derechos Humanos	http://ww3.museodelamemoria.cl
GLAM LIST	Museo Nacional de Historia Natural de Chile	http://www.mnhn.cl
GLAM LIST	Hrvatska akademija znanosti i umjetnosti	http://info.hazu.hr
GLAM LIST	Nacionalna i sveučilišna knjižnica u Zagrebu	http://www.nsk.hr
GLAM LIST	Arbejdmuseet	https://www.arbejdmuseet.dk
GLAM LIST	Den Hirschsprungske Samling	http://www.hirschsprung.dk
GLAM LIST	Det Kongelige Bibliotek	https://www.kb.dk
GLAM LIST	Frederiksberg Stadsarkiv	https://stadsarkivet.frederiksberg.dk
GLAM LIST	Københavns Museum	https://cphmuseum.kk.dk
GLAM LIST	Københavns Stadsarkiv	https://kbharkiv.dk
GLAM LIST	Kolding Stadsarkiv	https://stadsarkiv.kolding.dk

GLAM LIST	Magasin du Nord Museum	http://magasinmuseum.dk
GLAM LIST	Nationalmuseet	http://samlinger.natmus.dk
GLAM LIST	Nivaagaards Malerisamling	http://www.nivaagaard.dk
GLAM LIST	Slots- og Kulturstyrelsen	https://slks.dk
GLAM LIST	Statens Museum for Kunst	http://www.smk.dk
GLAM LIST	Sydvestjyske Museer	http://sol.sydvestjyskemuseer.dk
GLAM LIST	Thorvaldsens Museum	https://www.thorvaldsensmuseum.dk
GLAM LIST	Tjóðsavn Føroya	https://www.tjodsavnid.fo
GLAM LIST	Eesti Kunstimuseum	https://kunstimuseum.ekm.ee
GLAM LIST	Eesti Rahvusraamatukogu	http://www.nlib.ee
GLAM LIST	Järvakandi Klaasimuseum	https://www.klaasimuseum.ee
GLAM LIST	Muinsuskaitseamet	https://www.muinsuskaitseamet.ee
GLAM LIST	Rahvusarhiiv	http://www.ra.ee
GLAM LIST	Tartu Kunstimuseum	https://tartmus.ee
GLAM LIST	Võrumaa Muuseum	https://vorumuseum.ee
GLAM LIST	European Space Agency	https://www.esa.int
GLAM LIST	Aalto yliopiston arkisto	https://aalto.finna.fi
GLAM LIST	Gallen-Kallela Museo	http://www.gallen-kallela.fi
GLAM LIST	Helsingin kaupunginmuseo	http://www.helsinginkaupunginmuseo.fi
GLAM LIST	Kansallisarkisto	https://www.arkisto.fi
GLAM LIST	Kansallisgalleria	https://www.kansallisgalleria.fi
GLAM LIST	Kansalliskirjasto	https://www.kansalliskirjasto.fi
GLAM LIST	Kansallismuseo	https://www.kansallismuseo.fi
GLAM LIST	Museovirasto	https://www.museovirasto.fi

GLAM LIST	Satakunnan Museo	https://www.pori.fi/satakunnanmuseo
GLAM LIST	Sotamuseo	https://sotamuseo.fi
GLAM LIST	Suomen ilmailumuseo (Finnish Aviation Museum)	https://ilmailumuseo.fi
GLAM LIST	Suomen merimuseo (Finnish Maritime Museum)	http://www.kansallismuseo.fi/fi/suomen-merimuseo
GLAM LIST	Suomen valokuvataiteen museo	http://www.valokuvataiteenmuseo.fi
GLAM LIST	Svenska litteratursällskapet i Finland	http://www.sls.fi
GLAM LIST	Vantaan kaupunginmuseo (Vantaa City Museum)	https://sivistysvantaa.fi/vantaankaupunginmuseo/index.html
GLAM LIST	Yleisradio Oy	https://yle.fi
GLAM LIST	Alliance Israelite Universelle	http://www.jewishvirtuallibrary.org/alliance-israelite-universelle
GLAM LIST	Archives départementales de la Charente	https://archives.charente-maritime.fr
GLAM LIST	Archives départementales des Ardennes	https://cd08.fr
GLAM LIST	Archives départementales des Hauts-de-Seine	http://archives.hauts-de-seine.fr
GLAM LIST	Archives départementales du Calvados	https://archives.calvados.fr
GLAM LIST	Archives départementales du Finistère	https://archives.finistere.fr
GLAM LIST	Archives départementales du Jura	http://archives39.fr
GLAM LIST	Archives municipales de Limoges	https://archives.limoges.fr
GLAM LIST	Archives municipales de Toulouse	https://www.archives.toulouse.fr

GLAM LIST	Babord-Num (Université de Bordeaux)	https://www.u-bordeaux.com
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque de l'Institut national d'histoire de l'art	http://bibliotheque.inha.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque de Rennes Métropole	https://www.bibliotheques.rennes.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque et Centre de recherche en informatique de MINES ParisTech	https://www.cri.mines-paristech.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque Interuniversitaire de la Sorbonne	https://nubis.univ-paris1.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque interuniversitaire de Montpellier	https://www.biu-montpellier.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque interuniversitaire de Santé	http://www.biusante.parisdescartes.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque municipale de Grenoble	https://www.bm-grenoble.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque municipale de Lyon	https://www.bm-lyon.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque municipale de Nantes	https://bm.nantes.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque municipale de Toulouse	https://www.bibliotheque.toulouse.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque nationale et universitaire, Strasbourg	http://www.bnu.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque numérique de la ville de Périgueux	http://petrocoria-num.perigueux.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque numérique du Cirad en agronomie tropicale	https://numba.cirad.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque numérique du Limousin	https://bni-bfm.limoges.fr

GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque patrimoniale numérique de Mines ParisTech	www.mines-paristech.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque universitaire de Grenoble Alpes	https://bibliotheques.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque universitaire des langues et civilisations	https://www.bulac.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque virtuelle de l'université de Poitiers	https://www.univ-poitiers.fr
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèques de l'Ecole normale Supérieure-Paris	https://bib.ens.psl.eu
GLAM LIST	Centre des monuments nationaux	https://www.monuments-nationaux.fr
GLAM LIST	Centre National de la Danse	http://mediatheque.cnd.fr
GLAM LIST	École nationale vétérinaire de Toulouse	http://www.envt.fr
GLAM LIST	Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement	https://www.inrae.fr
GLAM LIST	La contemporaine	http://www.lacontemporaine.fr
GLAM LIST	Limédia - Bibliothèque numérique du Sillon lorrain	http://galeries.limedia.fr
GLAM LIST	Lo CIRDÒC (Occitanica)	http://www.locirdoc.fr
GLAM LIST	Maison de Balzac	https://www.maisondebaltzac.paris.fr
GLAM LIST	Maison de Victor Hugo	https://www.maisonsvictorhugo.paris.fr
GLAM LIST	Maison méditerranéenne des sciences de l'homme	https://www.mmsh.univ-aix.fr
GLAM LIST	Médiathèques Valence Romans Agglomération	http://mediatheques.valenceromansagglo.fr
GLAM LIST	Musée Bourdelle	https://www.bourdelle.paris.fr

GLAM LIST	Musée Carnavalet	https://www.carnavalet.paris.fr
GLAM LIST	Musée Cernuschi	https://www.cernuschi.paris.fr
GLAM LIST	Musee Cognacq-Jay	https://www.museecognacqjay.paris.fr
GLAM LIST	Musée d'art et d'histoire de Saint-Brieuc	http://www.saint-brieuc.fr/ville-dynamique/equipements-culturels/musee-dart-et-dhistoire
GLAM LIST	Musée d'art moderne de Paris	https://www.mam.paris.fr
GLAM LIST	Musée de Bretagne	https://www.musee-bretagne.fr
GLAM LIST	Musée de Die	https://www.museededie.org
GLAM LIST	Musée de la Libération de Paris	https://www.museeliberation-leclerc-moulin.paris.fr
GLAM LIST	Musée de la Vie romantique	https://museevieromantique.paris.fr
GLAM LIST	Musée des Augustins	https://www.augustins.org
GLAM LIST	Musée des Beaux-Arts de Reims	https://www.musees-reims.fr/fr/musees/musee-des-beaux-arts/
GLAM LIST	Musée Le Vergeur	https://musees-reims.fr/fr/musees/musee-le-vergeur/
GLAM LIST	Musée Saint-Raymond	https://saintraymond.toulouse.fr
GLAM LIST	Musée Saint-Remi	https://www.musees-reims.fr/fr/musees/musee-saint-remi/
GLAM LIST	Musées départementaux de la Haute-Saône	http://musees.haute-saone.fr
GLAM LIST	Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle	https://www.mnhn.fr
GLAM LIST	Petit Palais	https://www.petitpalais.paris.fr
GLAM LIST	Université de Caen Normandie	http://www.unicaen.fr/scd
GLAM LIST	Université de Lorraine	http://www.univ-lorraine.fr

GLAM LIST	Anhaltische Landesbücherei Dessau	http://www.bibliothek.dessau-rosslau.de
GLAM LIST	Architekturmuseum der TU Berlin	https://architekturmuseum.ub.tu-berlin.de
GLAM LIST	Arolsen Archives und KZ- Gedenkstätte Dachau	http://www.kz-gedenkstaette-dachau.de
GLAM LIST	Augustinermuseum	https://www.freiburg.de/pb/Lde/237748.html
GLAM LIST	AutoMuseum Volkswagen	https://www.automuseum-volkswagen.de
GLAM LIST	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	https://www.uni-weimar.de
GLAM LIST	Bayerische Akademie der Wissenschaften	http://www.badw.de
GLAM LIST	Bayerische Staatsgemäldesammlungen	https://www.pinakothek.de
GLAM LIST	Berlinische Galerie	https://berlinischegalerie.de
GLAM LIST	Bibliothek für Bildungsgeschichtliche Forschung	https://bbf.dipf.de
GLAM LIST	Botanischer Garten und Botanisches Museum Berlin	https://www.bgbm.org
GLAM LIST	Braunschweigisches Landesmuseum	https://3landesmuseen-braunschweig.de/braunschweigisches-landesmuseum
GLAM LIST	Brück & Sohn Kunstverlag Meißen	http://www.brueck-und-sohn.de
GLAM LIST	Bundesarchiv	https://www.bundesarchiv.de
GLAM LIST	Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg. Universitätsarchiv	https://uol.de/uni-archiv
GLAM LIST	Christian-Albrechts- Universität zu Kiel	http://www.uni-kiel.de
GLAM LIST	Computerspielemuseum	http://www.computerspielemuseum.de

GLAM LIST	DB Museum Nürnberg	https://www.dbmuseum.de
GLAM LIST	Deutsche Fotothek	http://www.deutschefotothek.de
GLAM LIST	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	https://www.dainst.org/dai/meldungen
GLAM LIST	Deutsches Buch- und Schriftmuseum der Deutschen Nationalbibliothek	https://www.dnb.de/DE/DBSM/dbsm_node.html
GLAM LIST	Deutsches Filminstitut - DIF	https://deutsches-filminstitut.de
GLAM LIST	Deutsches Museum	http://www.deutsches-museum.de
GLAM LIST	Deutsches Spielearchiv Nürnberg	http://www.deutsches-spiele-archiv.de
GLAM LIST	Deutsches Technikmuseum	http://www.sdtb.de
GLAM LIST	Digitales Naturhistorisches Archiv Darmstadt	https://www.dinarda.org
GLAM LIST	Emslandmuseum Lingen	https://emslandmuseum.de
GLAM LIST	Ernst-Haeckel-Haus der Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena	http://www.ehh.uni-jena.de
GLAM LIST	Ethnologisches Museum Berlin	https://www.smb.museum/museen-einrichtungen/ethnologisches-museum
GLAM LIST	Europäisches Brotmuseum	http://brotmuseum.de
GLAM LIST	Evenburg	https://evenburg.landkreis-leer.de
GLAM LIST	FHXB Friedrichshain-Kreuzberg Museum	https://www.fhxb-museum.de
GLAM LIST	Forschungsbibliothek Gotha der Universität Erfurt	https://www.uni-erfurt.de/bibliothek/fb
GLAM LIST	Generaldirektion der staatlichen Archive Bayerns	https://www.gda.bayern.de
GLAM LIST	Georg-August-Universität Göttingen. Physicalisches	http://physicalisches-cabinet.uni-goettingen.de/phycab/main.php

	Cabinet	
GLAM LIST	Georg-August-Universität Göttingen. Zentrale Kustodie	https://www.uni-goettingen.de/de/440706.html
GLAM LIST	Georg-Eckert-Institut – Leibniz-Institut für internationale Schulbuchforschung	http://www.gei.de
GLAM LIST	Gleimhaus - Museum der deutschen Aufklärung	http://www.gleimhaus.de
GLAM LIST	Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Bibliothek	https://www.gwlb.de
GLAM LIST	Haus der Geschichte Baden-Württemberg	http://www.hdgbw.de
GLAM LIST	Heidelberger Akademie der Wissenschaften	http://www.haw.uni-heidelberg.de
GLAM LIST	Heimatismuseum Obernfeld	https://www.obernfeld.de/index.php/museum
GLAM LIST	Herzog Anton Ulrich- Museum	https://3landesmuseen- braunschweig.de/herzog-anton-ulrich-museum
GLAM LIST	Herzog August Bibliothek Wolfenbüttel	https://www.hab.de
GLAM LIST	Hessisches Landesarchiv	https://landesarchiv.hessen.de
GLAM LIST	Historisches Museum am Hohen Ufer	https://www.hannover.de/Kultur- Freizeit/Museen- Ausstellungen/Museumsf%C3%BChrer/Top- Museen/Historisches-Museum-Hannover
GLAM LIST	Historisches Museum Frankfurt	http://www.historisches-museum-frankfurt.de
GLAM LIST	Hochschule für Musik und Theater "Felix Mendelssohn Bartholdy" Leipzig, Bibliothek/Archiv	https://www.hmt-leipzig.de/bibliothek
GLAM LIST	Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft Berlin, Historisches Archiv	https://www.htw- berlin.de/einrichtungen/zentrale- hochschulverwaltung/technische-

		dienste/hochschularchiv
GLAM LIST	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Institut für Kunst- und Bildgeschichte	http://www.kunstgeschichte.hu-berlin.de
GLAM LIST	Institut für Klassische Archäologie der FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg, Antikensammlung	https://www.fau.de/universitaet/das-ist-die-fau/sammlungen-der-fau/antikensammlung
GLAM LIST	Institut für Stadtgeschichte Frankfurt am Main, Abteilung Zeitgeschichte und Gedenken	https://www.stadtgeschichte-ffm.de/de/info-und-service/aufgaben-des-instituts/gedenken
GLAM LIST	Institut für Theaterwissenschaft der FU Berlin	https://www.geisteswissenschaften.fu-berlin.de/we07
GLAM LIST	International Tracing Service (ITS)	https://www.its-arolsen.org
GLAM LIST	Johann Wolfgang Goethe-Universität Frankfurt am Main	http://www.goethe-university-frankfurt.de
GLAM LIST	Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz	http://www.uni-mainz.de
GLAM LIST	Jüdisches Leben in Unterfranken (e.V.) / Stadt- und Stiftsarchiv Aschaffenburg	https://juedisches-unterfranken.de
GLAM LIST	Jüdisches Museum Berlin	http://www.jmberlin.de
GLAM LIST	Katholische Universität Eichstätt-Ingolstadt	http://www.ku.de
GLAM LIST	Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung	https://www.kas.de
GLAM LIST	Kreis- und Stadtarchäologie Gifhorn	https://www.gifhorn.de/wirtschaft-und-wohnen/bauen-und-wohnen/denkmalerschutz-archaeologie/bodendenkmalpflege-archaeologie
GLAM LIST	Kreisarchäologie Rotenburg	http://www.archaeologie-row.de

	(Wümme)	
GLAM LIST	Landesarchiv Baden-Württemberg	https://www.landesarchiv-bw.de
GLAM LIST	Landesmuseum Natur und Mensch	https://www.naturundmensch.de
GLAM LIST	Landesmuseum Württemberg	http://www.landesmuseum-stuttgart.de
GLAM LIST	Leibniz-Institut für Astrophysik Potsdam (AIP)	http://www.aip.de
GLAM LIST	Leibniz-Institut für Länderkunde e.V., Geographische Zentralbibliothek	http://www.ifl-leipzig.de
GLAM LIST	Leibniz-Institut für Ost- und Südosteuropaforschung (IOS)	https://www.ios-regensburg.de
GLAM LIST	Leipziger Städtische Bibliotheken	https://stadtbibliothek.leipzig.de
GLAM LIST	Lette-Verein Stiftung des öffentlichen Rechts Berlin / Bereich Bibliothek und Archiv	http://www.letteverein.berlin/ueber-uns/lette-archiv
GLAM LIST	Lindenau-Museum Altenburg	http://www.lindenau-museum.de
GLAM LIST	Martinus-Bibliothek - Wissenschaftliche Diözesanbibliothek - Mainz	http://dcms.bistummainz.de/bm/dcms/sites/einrichtungen/martinus-bibliothek/index.html
GLAM LIST	Max-Planck-Institut für Wissenschaftsgeschichte	https://www.mpiwg-berlin.mpg.de
GLAM LIST	Monacensia im Hildebrandhaus	http://www.monacensia.net/Hildebrandhaus.htm
GLAM LIST	Münchner Stadtmuseum	https://www.muenchner-stadtmuseum.de
GLAM LIST	Museum August Kestner	https://www.hannover.de/Museum-August-Kestner

GLAM LIST	Museum Burg Posterstein	http://www.burg-posterstein.de
GLAM LIST	Museum der Universität Tübingen MUT	https://www.unimuseum.uni-tuebingen.de
GLAM LIST	Museum für Abgüsse Klassischer Bildwerke	http://www.abgussmuseum.de
GLAM LIST	Museum für Hamburgische Geschichte	https://shmh.de/de/museum-fuer-hamburgische-geschichte
GLAM LIST	Museum für Kommunikation Nürnberg, Museumsstiftung Post und Telekommunikation	http://www.mfk-nuernberg.de
GLAM LIST	Museum für Kunst und Gewerbe Hamburg	https://www.mkg-hamburg.de
GLAM LIST	Museum für Naturkunde Berlin	http://www.naturkundemuseum.berlin
GLAM LIST	Museum für Neue Kunst	https://www.freiburg.de/pb/,Lde/237742.html
GLAM LIST	Museum Hameln	https://museumhameln.de
GLAM LIST	Museum Natur und Mensch	https://www.freiburg.de/pb/238070.html
GLAM LIST	Museum Schloss Fürstenberg	https://www.fuerstenberg-schloss.com
GLAM LIST	Museum Schloss Herzberg	https://www.mvnb.de/museumssuche/detail/museum-schloss-herzberg-am-harz
GLAM LIST	Museumsdorf Cloppenburg – Niedersächsisches Freilichtmuseum	http://www.museumsdorf.de
GLAM LIST	Museumsstiftung Post und Telekommunikation	http://www.museumsstiftung.de
GLAM LIST	Niedersächsische Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Göttingen	https://www.sub.uni-goettingen.de
GLAM LIST	Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege	https://denkmalpflege.niedersachsen.de

GLAM LIST	Niedersächsisches Landesarchiv	https://nla.niedersachsen.de
GLAM LIST	Niedersächsisches Landesmuseum Hannover	https://www.landmuseum-hannover.de
GLAM LIST	Oberharzer Bergwerksmuseum	https://www.oberharzerbergwerksmuseum.de
GLAM LIST	Portal zur Geschichte e.V.	https://www.portal-zur-geschichte.de
GLAM LIST	Rechnermuseum der GWDG	https://www.gwdg.de/web/guest/about-us/computer-museum
GLAM LIST	Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn	https://www.ulb.uni-bonn.de
GLAM LIST	Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn. Abteilung für Altamerikanistik	https://www.iae.uni-bonn.de
GLAM LIST	Sächsische Landesbibliothek - Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Dresden (SLUB)	https://www.slub-dresden.de
GLAM LIST	Salomon Ludwig Steinheim-Institut	http://www.steinheim-institut.de
GLAM LIST	Schulmuseum Bremen	https://www.schulmuseum-bremen.de
GLAM LIST	Sorbisches Institut Bautzen e.V.	https://www.serbski-institut.de
GLAM LIST	Staatliche Kunsthalle Karlsruhe	https://www.kunsthalle-karlsruhe.de
GLAM LIST	Staatliche Kunstsammlungen Dresden	https://www.skd.museum
GLAM LIST	Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Bremen	https://www.suub.uni-bremen.de
GLAM LIST	Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Hamburg Carl von Ossietzky	http://www.sub.uni-hamburg.de

GLAM LIST	Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin	http://staatsbibliothek-berlin.de
GLAM LIST	Städel Museum	http://www.staedelmuseum.de
GLAM LIST	Stadt Leipzig, Stadtarchiv	https://www.leipzig.de/wirtschaft-und-wissenschaft/bibliotheken-und-archiv/stadtarchiv
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv Darmstadt	https://landesarchiv.hessen.de
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv Hannover	https://www.hannover.de/Leben-in-der-Region-Hannover/Bildung/Bibliotheken-Archive/Stadtarchiv-Hannover
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv Kerpen	https://www.stadt-kerpen.de/stadtarchiv
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv Linz am Rhein	https://linz.de/stadtarchiv
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv Lüneburg	https://www.hansestadtlueneburg.de/Home-Hansestadt-Lueneburg/Gesellschaft-Soziales-und-Bildung/Bildung-hansestadt-lueneburg/Stadtarchiv-hansestadt-lueneburg.aspx
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv Speyer	http://www.stadtarchiv-speyer.findbuch.net
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv Stuttgart	http://www.stuttgart.de/stadtarchiv
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv Verden (Aller)	https://www.verden.de/portal/seiten/das-stadtarchiv-907000264-20680.html?rubrik=907000025
GLAM LIST	Stadtgeschichtliches Museum Leipzig	https://www.stadtgeschichtliches-museum-leipzig.de
GLAM LIST	Städtische Galerie im Lenbachhaus	https://www.lenbachhaus.de
GLAM LIST	Stadtmuseum Deggendorf	https://kulturviertel.deggendorf.de
GLAM LIST	Stadtmuseum Einbeck	https://stadtmuseumeinbeck.wpcomstaging.com
GLAM LIST	Stadtmuseum Landsberg am Lech	https://museum-landsberg.de
GLAM LIST	Stadtmuseum Tübingen	https://www.tuebingen.de/stadtmuseum

GLAM LIST	Stiftung Berliner Mauer	https://www.stiftung-berliner-mauer.de
GLAM LIST	Stiftung Haus der Geschichte der Bundesrepublik Deutschland	https://www.hdg.de
GLAM LIST	Stiftung Schloss Friedenstein	http://www.stiftungfriedenstein.de
GLAM LIST	Stiftung Stadtmuseum Berlin	https://www.stadtmuseum.de
GLAM LIST	Südsee-Sammlung und Historisches Museum Obergünzburg	https://www.suedseesammlung.de
GLAM LIST	Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB). Lab Nicht-Textuelle Materialien (NTM)	https://www.tib.eu/de/forschung-entwicklung/nicht-textuelle-materialien
GLAM LIST	Technische Universität Berlin	http://www.tu-berlin.de
GLAM LIST	Thüringer Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Jena	http://www.thulb.uni-jena.de
GLAM LIST	Überseemuseum	https://www.uebersee-museum.de
GLAM LIST	Universität Leipzig, Humboldt Lehrstuhl für Digital Humanities	http://www.dh.uni-leipzig.de
GLAM LIST	Universität zu Köln	https://www.portal.uni-koeln.de/uoc_home.html
GLAM LIST	Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Darmstadt	https://www.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de
GLAM LIST	Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Sachsen- Anhalt	http://bibliothek.uni-halle.de
GLAM LIST	Universitätsbibliothek Braunschweig	https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/ub
GLAM LIST	Universitätsbibliothek Chemnitz	https://www.tu-chemnitz.de/ub
GLAM LIST	Universitätsbibliothek der	http://www.ub.uni-muenchen.de

	Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München	
GLAM LIST	Universitätsbibliothek FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg	https://www.ub.fau.de
GLAM LIST	Universitätsbibliothek Freiberg	http://tu-freiberg.de
GLAM LIST	Universitätsbibliothek Heidelberg	http://www.ub.uni-heidelberg.de
GLAM LIST	Universitätsbibliothek Johann Christian Senckenberg	https://www.ub.uni-frankfurt.de
GLAM LIST	Universitätsbibliothek Kassel – Landesbibliothek und Murhardsche Bibliothek der Stadt Kassel	http://www.uni-kassel.de/ub/index.php
GLAM LIST	Universitätsbibliothek Leipzig	http://www.ub.uni-leipzig.de
GLAM LIST	Universitätsbibliothek Stuttgart	https://www.ub.uni-stuttgart.de
GLAM LIST	Veikkos--archiv	http://www.veikkos-archiv.com
GLAM LIST	Verwaltungsinformationszen- trum des Bezirksamtes Charlottenburg- Wilmersdorf von Berlin	https://www.berlin.de/ba-charlottenburg-wilmersdorf/verwaltung/interne-dienste/verwaltungsinformationszentrum-viz/
GLAM LIST	Wegemuseum Wusterhausen	http://www.wegemuseum.de
GLAM LIST	Weltkulturen Museum	http://www.weltkulturenmuseum.de
GLAM LIST	Wendland-Archiv	https://www.wendland-archiv.de
GLAM LIST	Zentral- und Landesbibliothek Berlin	https://www.zlb.de
GLAM LIST	Zentralinstitut für Kunstgeschichte	https://www.zikg.eu
GLAM LIST	Zeppelin Museum Friedrichshafen	http://www.zeppelin-museum.de

GLAM LIST	Zoologisches Forschungsmuseum Alexander Koenig	https://www.zfmk.de
GLAM LIST	Αποθετήριο Δήμου Τριπόλεως (Municipality of Tripoli)	http://tripoli.culhub.gr
GLAM LIST	Αποθετήριο Δήμου Χαϊδαρίου (Municipality of Haidari)	http://haidari.culhub.gr
GLAM LIST	Αρχείο Καβάφη (Cavafy Archive)	https://cavafy.onassis.org
GLAM LIST	Γενικά Αρχεία Κράτους, Αρχεία Νομού Ροδόπης (General State Archives - Regional Archives of Rodopi)	http://gak.rod.sch.gr
GLAM LIST	Κοινωφελής Επιχείρηση του Δήμου Μάνδρας - Ειδυλλίας (Charity Company of the Municipality of Mandra- Eidyllia)	http://mandra.evolution-isa.gr
GLAM LIST	Λαογραφικό Μουσείο Μετσόβου (Metsovo Folk Art Museum)	http://metsovomuseum.gr
GLAM LIST	Φιλολογικός σύλλογος Παρνασσός (Parnassos Literary Society)	http://www.lsparnas.gr
GLAM LIST	Ψηφιακή Συλλογή ιστορικών Ελληνικών περιοδικών της Βιβλιοθήκης και Κέντρου Πληροφόρησης του Πανεπιστημίου Πατρών (Digital Library of Pleia, University of Patras)	http://pleias.lis.upatras.gr
GLAM LIST	Ψηφιακό αποθετήριο Ιστορικού και πολιτιστικού αρχείου Στέφανου Κότσιανου" (Digital Repository of the Historical and Cultural Archive of	http://kotsianos.evolution-isa.gr

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GLAM LIST	Csorba Győző Könyvtár	http://www.csgyk.hu
GLAM LIST	Debreceni Egyetem	http://www.lib.unideb.hu
GLAM LIST	Déri Múzeum	http://www.derimuzeum.hu
GLAM LIST	Eötvös Loránd Tudományegyetem Egyetemi Könyvtár	https://www.konyvtar.elte.hu
GLAM LIST	Fejér György Városi Könyvtár	http://www.fgyvk.hu
GLAM LIST	Fővárosi Szabó Ervin Könyvtár Központi Könyvtár	http://www.fszek.hu
GLAM LIST	Hollóházi Porcelánmúzeum	http://www.hollohazi.hu
GLAM LIST	II. Rákóczi Ferenc Megyei Könyvtár	https://www.rfmliib.hu
GLAM LIST	Kuny Domokos Megyei Múzeum	http://kunymuzeum.hu
GLAM LIST	Magyar Ferences Könyvtár és Levéltár	http://mfkl.ferencesek.hu
GLAM LIST	Rippl-Rónai Múzeum	http://www.smmi.hu
GLAM LIST	Schola Graphidis Művészeti Gyűjtemény Magyarország	https://scholagraphidis.omeka.net
GLAM LIST	Semmelweis Orvostörténeti Múzeum	http://www.semmelweis.museum.hu
GLAM LIST	Ljósmyndasafn Reykjavíkur	http://borgarsogusafn.is
GLAM LIST	DAG Museums	https://dagworld.com
GLAM LIST	Dewantara Kirti Griya	
GLAM LIST	Museum Dr. H.C. Oemboe Hina Kapita	

GLAM LIST	Museum Pusat TNI AU Dirgantara Mandala	
GLAM LIST	Museum Uang Sumatera	
GLAM LIST	Yayasan Sastra Lestari	https://www.sastra.org
GLAM LIST	Biodiversity Heritage Library	https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Khalili Collections	https://www.khalilicollections.org
GLAM LIST	UNESCO Archives	https://unesdoc.unesco.org/archives
GLAM LIST	Digital Heritage Age (Digital Counties Initiative)	https://www.digitalheritageage.com
GLAM LIST	Glucksman Library (University of Limerick)	http://www.ul.ie/library
GLAM LIST	Hunt Museum	http://www.huntmuseum.com
GLAM LIST	National Gallery of Ireland	https://www.nationalgallery.ie
GLAM LIST	National Library of Ireland	http://www.nli.ie
GLAM LIST	National Museum of Ireland	https://www.museum.ie
GLAM LIST	ספרייה הלאומית (National Library of Israel)	http://web.nli.org.il
GLAM LIST	Archivio Pietro Pensa	http://archivio.pietro.pensa.it
GLAM LIST	Archivio Storico Ricordi	https://www.archivioricordi.com
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Europea di Informazione e Cultura	http://www.beic.it
GLAM LIST	Dipartimento di Scienze della Vita, Università degli Studi di Trieste	http://dbiodbs.units.it/carso/chiavi_pub00
GLAM LIST	Dr. Friederich Tessmann Provincial Library	http://www.tessmann.it
GLAM LIST	Fondazione Ranieri di Sorbello	http://www.fondazioneranieri.org
GLAM LIST	Museo Egizio, Torino	https://museoegizio.it

GLAM LIST	Raccolte extraeuropee del Castello Sforzesco	https://www.milanocastello.it
GLAM LIST	九州国立博物館 (Kyushu National Museum)	http://www.kyuhaku.jp
GLAM LIST	京都国立博物館 (Kyoto National Museum)	http://www.kyohaku.go.jp
GLAM LIST	国土地理院 (Geospatial Information Authority of Japan)	https://www.gsi.go.jp/
GLAM LIST	国立国会図書館 (National Diet Library)	http://www.ndl.go.jp
GLAM LIST	奈良国立博物館 (Nara National Museum)	https://www.narahaku.go.jp
GLAM LIST	愛知県美術館 (Aichi Prefectural Museum of Art)	https://www-art.aac.pref.aichi.jp/en/index.html
GLAM LIST	東京国立博物館 (Tokyo National Museum)	http://www.tnm.jp
GLAM LIST	東京富士美術館 (Tokyo Fuji Art Museum)	https://www.fujibi.or.jp
GLAM LIST	群馬県立図書館 (Gunma Prefectural Library)	https://www.library.pref.gunma.jp
GLAM LIST	Latvijas Nacionālā bibliotēka	https://www.lnb.lv
GLAM LIST	Kauno IX forto muziejus	http://www.9fortomuziejus.lt
GLAM LIST	Kupiškio etnografijos muziejus	http://etnografijosmuziejus.lt
GLAM LIST	Lietuvos dailės muziejus	https://www.ldm.lt

GLAM LIST	Maironio lietuvių literatūros muziejaus	http://maironiomuziejus.lt
GLAM LIST	Rokiškio krašto muziejus	http://www.muzejusrokiskyje.lt
GLAM LIST	Šiaulių „Aušros“ muziejus	http://ausrosmuziejus.lt
GLAM LIST	Žemaičių muziejus „Alka”	http://www.muzejusalka.lt
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque nationale de Luxembourg	http://www.bnl.public.lu
GLAM LIST	Archivo Histórico General del Estado de Sinaloa	https://ahgs.gob.mx
GLAM LIST	Ayuntamiento de Reynosa	https://www.reynosa.gob.mx
GLAM LIST	Garros Galería	http://www.garrosccr.com
GLAM LIST	Museo de Arte Popular de la Ciudad de México	http://www.map.df.gob.mx
GLAM LIST	Museo del Objeto del Objeto	https://www.elmodo.mx
GLAM LIST	Museo Soumaya	http://www.museosoumaya.org
GLAM LIST	African Studies Centre Leiden	https://www.ascleiden.nl
GLAM LIST	Amsterdam Museum	https://www.amsterdammuseum.nl
GLAM LIST	Bakkerij Museum	https://www.bakkerijmuseum.nl
GLAM LIST	Bibliotheek der Rijksuniversiteit Leiden	https://www.bibliotheek.universiteitleiden.nl
GLAM LIST	Circus Museum	http://circusmuseum.nl
GLAM LIST	CODA Apeldoorn	https://www.coda-apeldoorn.nl
GLAM LIST	Deventer Musea	https://www.deventer.nl/musea
GLAM LIST	Erfgoed 's-Hertogenbosch	https://www.erfgoedshertogenbosch.nl
GLAM LIST	Erfgoedhuis Zuid-Holland	https://www.erfgoedhuis-zh.nl
GLAM LIST	Flipje and Streekmuseum Tiel	http://streekmuseumtiel.nl

GLAM LIST	Gemeentearchief Weert	https://beeldbankwo2.nl
GLAM LIST	Gemeentearchief Zaanstad	https://archieff.zaanstad.nl
GLAM LIST	Het Nederlands Instituut voor Militaire Historie	https://defensie.nl/nimh
GLAM LIST	Het Nieuwe Instituut	http://www.hetnieuweinstituut.nl
GLAM LIST	Het Utrechts Archief	http://www.hetutrechtsarchief.nl
GLAM LIST	Historisch Museum Ede	http://www.historischmuseumede.nl
GLAM LIST	Huis Bergh	https://huisbergh.nl
GLAM LIST	Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies	http://www.ihs.nl
GLAM LIST	Koninklijk Instituut voor Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde	https://www.kitlv.nl
GLAM LIST	Koninklijke Bibliotheek	http://www.kb.nl
GLAM LIST	Liemers Museum	http://www.liemersmuseum.nl
GLAM LIST	Limburgs Museum	https://www.limburgsmuseum.nl
GLAM LIST	Mauritshuis	http://www.mauritshuis.nl
GLAM LIST	Museon	https://www.museon.nl
GLAM LIST	Museum Catharijneconvent	https://www.catharijneconvent.nl
GLAM LIST	Museum Rotterdam	https://museumrotterdam.nl
GLAM LIST	Nationaal Archief	https://www.nationaalarchief.nl
GLAM LIST	Nationaal Glas Museum	http://www.nationaalglasmuseum.nl
GLAM LIST	Nationaal Museum van Wereldculturen	https://www.tropenmuseum.nl/nl/over-het-tropenmuseum/stichting-nationaal-museum-van-wereldculturen
GLAM LIST	Naturalis Biodiversity Center	http://www.naturalis.nl
GLAM LIST	Nederlands Instituut voor Beeld en Geluid	https://beeldengeluid.nl

GLAM LIST	Nederlands Instituut voor Militaire Historie	https://www.defensie.nl/onderwerpen/militaire-geschiedenis-nimh
GLAM LIST	Openluchtmuseum	https://openluchtmuseum.nl
GLAM LIST	Regionaal Archief Alkmaar	https://www.regionaalarchiefalkmaar.nl
GLAM LIST	Regionaal Archief Nijmegen	https://regionaalarchiefnijmegen.nl
GLAM LIST	Regionaal Archief Zutphen	http://www.regionaalarchiefzutphen.nl
GLAM LIST	Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed	https://beeldbank.cultureelerfgoed.nl
GLAM LIST	Rijksmuseum	http://www.rijksmuseum.nl
GLAM LIST	Rijksmuseum Twenthe	https://www.rijksmuseumtwenthe.nl
GLAM LIST	Rijksmuseum van Oudheden	http://www.rmo.nl
GLAM LIST	Schouwen-Duiveland	https://www.schouwen-duiveland.nl/inwoners/gemeentearchief
GLAM LIST	Slot Loevestein	https://www.slotloevestein.nl
GLAM LIST	Stadskasteel Zaltbommel	http://stadskasteelzaltbommel.nl
GLAM LIST	Stadsmuseum Harderwijk	https://www.stadsmuseum-harderwijk.nl
GLAM LIST	Stedelijk Museum Zutphen	http://www.museazutphen.nl
GLAM LIST	Tropenmuseum	https://www.tropenmuseum.nl
GLAM LIST	Universiteitsbibliotheek Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen	http://www.ru.nl/ubn
GLAM LIST	Universiteitsbibliotheek Utrecht	https://www.uu.nl/en/university-library
GLAM LIST	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	https://www.ub.vu.nl
GLAM LIST	Alexander Turnbull Library	https://natlib.govt.nz/collections/a-z/alexander-turnbull-library-collections
GLAM LIST	Archives New Zealand	http://archives.govt.nz

GLAM LIST	Auckland Art Gallery Toi o Tamaki	https://www.aucklandartgallery.com
GLAM LIST	Auckland Libraries - Heritage Images	http://www.aucklandcity.govt.nz/dbtw-wpd/heritageimages
GLAM LIST	Auckland War Memorial Museum	http://www.aucklandmuseum.com
GLAM LIST	Canterbury Museum	https://www.canterburymuseum.com
GLAM LIST	Dunedin City Council Archives	http://www.dunedin.govt.nz/services/archives
GLAM LIST	Forrester Gallery	https://culturewaitaki.org.nz/forrester-gallery
GLAM LIST	Hutt City Council	http://www.huttcity.govt.nz
GLAM LIST	Lincoln University	http://www.lincoln.ac.nz
GLAM LIST	MTG Hawke's Bay	https://www.mtghawkesbay.com
GLAM LIST	Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa	http://www.tepapa.govt.nz
GLAM LIST	Museum of Transport and Technology (MOTAT)	https://www.motat.org.nz
GLAM LIST	National Library of New Zealand	https://natlib.govt.nz
GLAM LIST	New Zealand Electronic Text Collection	http://nzetc.victoria.ac.nz
GLAM LIST	Palmerston North City Library	https://citylibrary.pncc.govt.nz
GLAM LIST	Sarjeant Gallery	http://www.sarjeant.org.nz
GLAM LIST	Te Papa Tongarewa Museum of New Zealand	http://www.tepapa.govt.nz
GLAM LIST	The Suter Art Gallery	http://thesuter.org.nz/
GLAM LIST	Wairarapa Archive	https://library.mstn.govt.nz/archive/wairarapa-archive
GLAM LIST	Waitaki Museum and	https://culturewaitaki.org.nz/waitaki-museum

	Archive	
GLAM LIST	Wellington City Archives	https://archivesonline.wcc.govt.nz
GLAM LIST	Anno – Museene i Hedmark	https://annomuseum.no
GLAM LIST	Arkeologisk museum i Stavanger	http://www.arkeologiskmuseum.no
GLAM LIST	Bergen Offentlige Bibliotek	https://bergenbibliotek.no
GLAM LIST	Domkirkeodden	https://domkirkeodden.no
GLAM LIST	Finnmark Fylkesbibliotek	http://www.fm.fylkesbibl.no
GLAM LIST	Fylkesarkivet i Sogn og Fjordane	https://www.fylkesarkivet.no
GLAM LIST	Glomdalsmuseet	https://glomdalsmuseet.no
GLAM LIST	Helgelands Museum	http://helgelandmuseum.no
GLAM LIST	Hvalfangstmuseet	http://www.hvalfangstmuseet.no
GLAM LIST	KODE Kunstmuseer og komponisthjem	https://www.kodebergen.no
GLAM LIST	Larvik Museum	http://www.larvikmuseum.no
GLAM LIST	Munchmuseet	http://www.munchmuseet.no
GLAM LIST	Musea i Nord-Østerdalen	https://museainordosterdalen.no
GLAM LIST	Museene for kystkultur og gjenreisning i Finnmark	http://www.kystmuseene.no
GLAM LIST	Museene i Sør-Trøndelag	https://mist.no
GLAM LIST	Museum Stavanger	https://www.museumstavanger.no
GLAM LIST	Museumssenteret i Hordaland	http://www.muho.no
GLAM LIST	Nasjonalbiblioteket	http://www.nb.no/
GLAM LIST	Nasjonalmuseet	https://www.nasjonalmuseet.no
GLAM LIST	Nordfjord Folkemuseum	http://www.nordfjord.museum.no

GLAM LIST	Nordlandsmuseet	http://www.nordlandsmuseet.no
GLAM LIST	Norsk Folkemuseum	https://norskfolkemuseum.no/norskfarmasihistoriskmuseum
GLAM LIST	Norsk Industriarbeidermuseum	https://nia.no
GLAM LIST	Norsk Maritimt Museum	https://marmuseum.no
GLAM LIST	Norsk Skogmuseum	https://skogmus.no
GLAM LIST	Norsk Teknisk Museum	http://www.tekniskmuseum.no
GLAM LIST	Oslo byarkiv	https://www.oslo.kommune.no
GLAM LIST	Oslo Museum	https://www.oslomuseum.no
GLAM LIST	Preus Museum	http://www.preusmuseum.no
GLAM LIST	Riksarkivet	https://www.arkivverket.no
GLAM LIST	SFKM - Sogn og Fjordane Kunstmuseum	https://sfkm.no
GLAM LIST	Slottsfjellsmuseet	http://www.slottsfjellsmuseet.no
GLAM LIST	Sunnfjord Museum	http://www.sunnfjord.museum.no
GLAM LIST	Telemuseet	http://telemuseet.no
GLAM LIST	Tromsø Museum	https://uit.no/om/enhet/tmu/tmu
GLAM LIST	Universitetet i Bergen	http://www.uib.no/en/universitymuseum
GLAM LIST	Varanger museum IKS	https://www.varangermuseum.no
GLAM LIST	Vest-Telemark Museum	http://www.vest-telemark.museum.no
GLAM LIST	Vestfoldmuseene	http://www.vestfoldmuseene.no
GLAM LIST	Vitenskapsmuseet	http://www.ntnu.no/vitenskapsmuseet
GLAM LIST	Akademia Sztuk Pięknych im. Jana Matejki w Krakowie	https://www.asp.krakow.pl
GLAM LIST	Archiwum Główne Akt	https://agad.gov.pl

	Dawnych	
GLAM LIST	Bałtycka Biblioteka Cyfrowa	https://bibliotekacyfrowa.eu
GLAM LIST	Biblioteka Narodowa	http://www.bn.org.pl
GLAM LIST	Biblioteka Uniwersytecka w Warszawie Biblioteka	http://www.buw.uw.edu.pl
GLAM LIST	Biblioteka Uniwersytecka we Wrocławiu Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://www.bibliotekacyfrowa.pl
GLAM LIST	Centrum Żydowskie w Oświęcimiu	https://ajcf.pl
GLAM LIST	Chelmska Biblioteka Publiczna	http://cyfrowa.chbp.chelm.pl
GLAM LIST	Cricoteka	https://www.cricoteka.pl
GLAM LIST	Cyfrowa Biblioteka Diecezjalna w Sandomierzu	http://bc.bdsandomierz.pl
GLAM LIST	Dąbrowski Dom Kultury	https://www.ddkdabrowa.pl
GLAM LIST	Dolnośląska Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://www.dbc.wroc.pl
GLAM LIST	Dom Grecki w Myślenicach	https://muzeum.myslenice.pl
GLAM LIST	Dom Rodzinny Ojca Świętego Jana Pawła II w Wadowicach	https://domjp2.pl
GLAM LIST	Elbląska Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://bibliotekaelblaska.pl
GLAM LIST	Galeria Sztuki Współczesnej "Bunkier Sztuki"	http://bunkier.art.pl
GLAM LIST	Instytut Badań Literackich PAN	http://ibl.waw.pl/pl/o-instytucie/biblioteka
GLAM LIST	Instytut Nauk Geologicznych Polskiej Akademii Nauk	https://www.ing.pan.pl
GLAM LIST	Jagiellońska Biblioteka Cyfrowa	https://jbc.bj.uj.edu.pl

GLAM LIST	Katedra Wawelska	http://www.katedra-wawelska.pl
GLAM LIST	Kujawsko-Pomorska Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://kpbc.umk.pl
GLAM LIST	Lodzka Akademska Siec Biblioteczna	http://cybra.lodz.pl
GLAM LIST	Małopolska Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://mbc.malopolska.pl
GLAM LIST	Marcin Mikula Locksmithing Museum	
GLAM LIST	Mazowiecka Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://mbc.cyfrowemazowsze.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Afrykanistyczne Olkusz	https://www.mok.olkusz.pl/index.php/muzea/29-muzeum-afrykanistyczne
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Archeologiczne w Krakowie	http://ma.krakow.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Archidiecezjalne w Krakowie	https://archimuzeum.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Armii Krajowej w Krakowie	https://muzeum-ak.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Benedyktynów w Tyńcu	http://kultura.benedyktyni.com/muzeum
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Farmacji Collegium Medicum Uniwersytetu Jagiellońskiego	http://www.muzeumfarmacji.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Geologiczne Wydziału Geologii, Geofizyki i Ochrony Środowiska Akademii Górniczo-Hutniczej	www.geol.agh.edu.pl/~muzeum
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Historii Fotografii w Krakowie	https://mufo.krakow.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Historyczne Miasta Krakowa	https://muzeumkrakowa.pl

GLAM LIST	Muzeum im. Aleksandra Kłosińskiego w Kętach	http://muzeum.kety.pl/strona_old/en
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Inżynierii Miejskiej w Krakowie	https://www.mim.krakow.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Lotnictwa Polskiego w Krakowie	https://muzeumlotnictwa.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Nadwiślański Park Etnograficzny w Wygielzowie i Zamek Lipowiec	http://mnpe.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Narodowe w Krakowie	https://mnk.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Narodowe w Warszawie	http://www.mnw.art.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Niepołomickie	https://muzeum.niepolomice.pl/zamek-krolewski
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Okręgowe w Nowym Sączu	http://muzeum.sacz.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Okręgowe w Tarnowie	https://muzeum.tarnow.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Orawski Park Etnograficzny w Zubrzycy Górnej	https://www.orawa.eu
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Przyrodnicze im. Krystyny i Włodzimierza Tomków w Ciężkowicach	http://muzeum.ciezkowice.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Regionalne PTTK im. Antoniego Minkiewicza w Olkuszu	http://pttkolkusz.pl/muzeum-regionalne/arichwum
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Regionalne PTTK im. Ignacego Łukasiewicza w Gorlicach	http://www.gorlice.pttk.pl/index.php?option=com_content&task=view&id=378&Itemid=33
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Regionalne PTTK im. Władysława Kowalskiego w Dobczycach	https://zamek.dobczyce.pl

GLAM LIST	Muzeum Regionalne w Piwnicznej-Zdroju	
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Sztuki i Techniki Japońskiej „Manggha”	https://manggha.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Sztuki w Łodzi	https://msl.org.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Sztuki Współczesnej w Krakowie	https://mocak.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Tatrzańskie im. dra Tytusa Chałubińskiego w Zakopanem	https://muzeumtatrzańskie.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Twórczości Władysława Wołkowskiego w Olkuzu	https://visitmalopolska.pl/obiekt/-/poi/muzeum-tworczosci-wladyslawa-wolkowskiego-olkusz
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Uniwersytetu Jagiellońskiego Collegium Maius	https://maius.uj.edu.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum w Chrzanowie im. Ireny i Mieczysława Mazarakich	https://muzeum.chrzanow.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Ziemi Bieckiej w Bieczu	http://www.muzeum.biecz.pl
GLAM LIST	Muzeum Żup Krakowskich Wieliczka	https://muzeum.wieliczka.pl
GLAM LIST	Podkarpacka Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://pbc.rzeszow.pl
GLAM LIST	Podlaska Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://pbc.biaman.pl
GLAM LIST	Politechnika Warszawska	http://www.bg.pw.edu.pl
GLAM LIST	Polska Akademia Umiejętności	http://www.pau.krakow.pl
GLAM LIST	Pomorska Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://pbc.gda.pl
GLAM LIST	Radomska Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://bc.radom.pl

GLAM LIST	Repozytorium Cyfrowe Instytutów Naukowych	http://rcin.org.pl
GLAM LIST	Seweryn Udziela Ethnographic Museum in Kraków	https://etnomuzeum.eu
GLAM LIST	Silesian Biblioteka Cyfrowa	https://www.sbc.org.pl
GLAM LIST	Sosenko Family Foundation	
GLAM LIST	Wejherowska Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://biblioteka.wejherowo.pl
GLAM LIST	Wielkopolska Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://www.wbc.poznan.pl
GLAM LIST	Zachęta Narodowa Galeria Sztuki	https://zacheta.art.pl
GLAM LIST	Zamek Królewski na Wawelu - Państwowe Zbiory Sztuki	https://wawel.krakow.pl
GLAM LIST	Ziemi Łódzkiej Biblioteka Cyfrowa	http://bc.wimbp.lodz.pl
GLAM LIST	Arquivo Teatro Nacional Dona Maria II	http://www.tndm.pt/pt/biblioteca-arquivo
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Nacional de Portugal	http://www.bnportugal.pt
GLAM LIST	Direção Regional da Cultura dos Açores	http://www.azores.gov.pt
GLAM LIST	Instituto de Investigação Científica Tropical	http://www.iict.pt
GLAM LIST	Montemor-o-Novo (Museu Virtual)	https://montemorbase.com
GLAM LIST	Museu da Cidade de Aveiro	http://mca.cm-aveiro.pt
GLAM LIST	Museu Nacional de Arqueologia	http://www.museunacionalarqueologia.gov.pt
GLAM LIST	Qatar National Digital	https://www.qdl.qa

	Library	
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Academiei Române	http://www.biblacad.ro
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Centrală Universitară "Lucian Blaga" din Cluj-Napoca	https://www.bcucluj.ro
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Județeană „Alexandru D. Xenopol” Arad	http://www.bibliotecaarad.ro
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Județeană G. T. Kirileanu Neamț	http://www.bibgtkneamt.ro
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Națională a României	http://www.bibnat.ro
GLAM LIST	Costică Acsinte Archive	http://colectiacosticaacsinte.eu
GLAM LIST	Institutul Național al Patrimoniului	http://clasate.cimec.ro
GLAM LIST	Εθνική Βιβλιοθήκη της Ρωσίας (National Library of Russia)	http://nlr.ru
GLAM LIST	Башкирский государственный университет	https://strbsu.ru/arch_museum
GLAM LIST	Государственный Дарвиновский музей	http://www.darwinmuseum.ru
GLAM LIST	Переславская неделя (Pereslavl Week)	http://www.pereslavl.ru/pn
GLAM LIST	РИА Новости (RIA Novosti)	http://visualrian.ru
GLAM LIST	Российская государственная библиотека (Russian State Library)	https://www.rsl.ru
GLAM LIST	Тульский государственный музей оружия	http://museum-arms.ru
GLAM LIST	Устная история (Oral	http://oralhistory.ru

	History Foundation)	
GLAM LIST	Эхо Москвы (Echo of Moscow)	http://www.echo.msk.ru
GLAM LIST	Музей воздухопловства — Београд (Belgrade Aeronautical Museum)	http://muzejvazduhoplovstva.org.rs
GLAM LIST	Универзитет у Београду (University of Belgrade)	http://www.bg.ac.rs
GLAM LIST	Galéria Miloša Alexandra Bazovského	http://www.gmab.sk
GLAM LIST	Galéria umelcov Spiša	http://www.gus.sk
GLAM LIST	Galéria umenia Ernesta Zmetáka v Nových Zámkoch	http://www.galerianz.eu
GLAM LIST	Liptovská galéria Petera Michala Bohúňa	http://www.galerialm.sk
GLAM LIST	Oravská galéria	http://www.oravskagalera.sk
GLAM LIST	Slovenská akadémia vied	http://ibot.sav.sk
GLAM LIST	Slovenská národná galéria	https://www.sng.sk
GLAM LIST	Digitalna knjižnica Slovenije	http://www.dlib.si
GLAM LIST	Goriška knjižnica Franceta Bevka	https://www.gkfb.si
GLAM LIST	Osrednja knjižnica Celje	https://www.knjiznica-celje.si
GLAM LIST	Ajuntament de Barcelona	https://bcnroc.ajuntament.barcelona.cat
GLAM LIST	Ajuntament de Girona	http://sgdap.girona.cat
GLAM LIST	Arxiu Nacional de Catalunya	http://anc.gencat.cat
GLAM LIST	Asociación de Amigos de los Caminos de Santiago de Madrid	http://www.demadridalcamino.org
GLAM LIST	Ateneu Barcelonès	http://www.ateneubcn.org

GLAM LIST	Biblioteca da Deputación de Ourense	https://biblioteca.depourense.es
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca da Escola Municipal de Artes e Oficios – Vigo	https://bibliotecadaemao.blogspot.com
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca de Catalunya	http://www.bnc.cat
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca de Galicia	http://bibliotecadegalicia.xunta.es
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Digital de Castilla y León	https://bibliotecadigital.jcyl.es
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Digital de la Comunidad de Madrid	http://bibliotecavirtualmadrid.org
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Dixital de Galicia	https://biblioteca.galiciana.gal
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca do Mosteiro de Poio	
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca do Museo de Pontevedra	https://museos.xunta.gal/es/pontevedra
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Municipal de Estudos Locais	https://www.coruna.gal/bibliotecas/gl/memoria-local
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Museu Víctor Balaguer	http://www.victorbalaguer.cat
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Nacional de España	http://www.bne.es
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Pública de Lugo	https://bibliotecas.xunta.gal/lugo
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Pública de Pontevedra Antonio Odriozola	https://bibliotecas.xunta.gal/pontevedra
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Seminario Santa Catalina - Diócese Mondoñedo-Ferrol	https://mondonedoferrol.org
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Valenciana Digital	http://bivaldi.gva.es
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Virtual Aragón	http://bibliotecavirtual.aragon.es/bva

GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Virtual de Andalucía	http://www.bibliotecavirtualdeandalucia.es
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Virtual de Asturias	https://bibliotecavirtual.asturias.es
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Virtual de Derecho Aragónés	http://www.derechoaragones.es
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Virtual de Ministerio de Defensa	http://bibliotecavirtualdefensa.es
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Virtual de Prensa Histórica	http://prensahistorica.mcu.es
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Virtual La Rioja	http://bibliotecavirtual.larioja.org
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca-Museo de Pontearreas	http://pontearreas.gal
GLAM LIST	Centre de Documentació de l'Orfeó Català	http://www.orfeocatala.cat
GLAM LIST	Ciconia: Biblioteca Digital del Patrimonio Cultural de Extremadura	http://ciconia.gobex.es
GLAM LIST	Euskal Liburutegi Digitala	http://www.liburuklik.euskadi.eus
GLAM LIST	Filmoteca de Catalunya	http://www.filmoteca.cat
GLAM LIST	Fundación Ignacio Larramendi	http://www.larramendi.es/es/inicio/inicio.do
GLAM LIST	Fundación Joaquín Díaz	https://funjdiaz.net
GLAM LIST	Fundación Penzol	https://hoxe.vigo.org/movemonos/m_penzol.php
GLAM LIST	Galiciana, Biblioteca de Galicia	http://biblioteca.galiciana.gal
GLAM LIST	Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya	http://www.icgc.cat
GLAM LIST	Institut Ramon Llull	https://www.llull.cat
GLAM LIST	Instituto Andaluz del Patrimonio Histórico	http://www.iaph.es

GLAM LIST	Instituto de Educación Secundaria Lucus Augusti	http://www.edu.xunta.gal/centros/ieslucusaugusti
GLAM LIST	Museo das Peregrinacións e de Santiago	https://museoperegrinacions.xunta.gal
GLAM LIST	Museo de Arte Africano Arellano Alonso	http://www.fundacionjimenezarellano.com
GLAM LIST	Museo de Historia de Madrid	https://www.madrid.es/portales/munimadrid/es/Inicio/Cultura-ocio-y-deporte/Cultura-y-ocio/Museo-de-Historia-de-Madrid
GLAM LIST	Museo del Romanticismo	http://www.culturaydeporte.gob.es/mromanticismo/inicio.html
GLAM LIST	Museo del Traje	http://www.culturaydeporte.gob.es/mtraje/inicio.html
GLAM LIST	Museo do Pobo Galego	http://www.museodopobo.gal
GLAM LIST	Museo Massó	https://museos.xunta.gal/gl/masso
GLAM LIST	Museo Nacional de Cerámica y Artes Suntuarias González Martí	http://mnceramica.mcu.es
GLAM LIST	Museo Sorolla	http://museosorolla.mcu.es
GLAM LIST	Museus de Sitges	http://museusdesitges.cat
GLAM LIST	Real Academia Galega	https://academia.gal
GLAM LIST	Real Academia Nacional de Medicina	https://www.ranm.es
GLAM LIST	Universidade de Santiago de Compostela	http://www.usc.es
GLAM LIST	Universitat de Barcelona	http://www.ub.edu
GLAM LIST	Universitat de Lleida	http://www.udl.es
GLAM LIST	Universitat Pompeu Fabra	https://www.upf.edu
GLAM LIST	Ájtte, Svenskt Fjäll- och Samemuseum	www.ajtte.com

GLAM LIST	Arbetets museum	https://www.arbetetsmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Arboga kommuns fotoarkiv	https://www.arboga.se
GLAM LIST	ArkDes	https://arkdes.se
GLAM LIST	Armémuseum	http://www.armemuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Arsenalen	http://arsenalen.se
GLAM LIST	Bild Linköping	https://www.linkoping.se/uppleva-och-gora/Arkiv/bild-linkoping
GLAM LIST	Blekinge museum	https://www.blekingemuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Bohusläns museum	http://www.bohuslansmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Burlövs kommun	https://www.burlov.se/kommunpolitik/saarbetarvimed/kommunarkiv.4.61db301015981f64489b878d.html
GLAM LIST	Dalarna museum	https://dalarnasmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Enköpings museum	https://enkoping.se/underwebbar/enkopingsmuseum.html
GLAM LIST	Eskilstuna kommun	https://www.eskilstuna.se/uppleva-och-gora/bibliotek-arkiv-och-lokalhistoria/lokalhistoria---eskilskallan/om-eskilskallan---kontakta-oss/eskilstunastadsarkiv-i-eskilskallan.html
GLAM LIST	Etnografiska museet	http://www.varldskulturmuseerna.se/etnografiskamuseet
GLAM LIST	Falbygdens museum	https://www.falkoping.se/upplevagora/falbygdenmuseum/besokoss.4.65933fa8123bf80c6558000230.html
GLAM LIST	Flygvapenmuseum	http://www.flygvapenmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Folklivsarkivet med Skånes musiksamlingar, Lunds universitet	https://www.folklivsarkivet.lu.se
GLAM LIST	Föreningsarkivet i Sydvästra Götaland	http://foreningsarkivet-svg.se

GLAM LIST	Göteborgs naturhistoriska museum	http://www.gnm.se
GLAM LIST	Göteborgs stadsmuseum	https://goteborgsstadsmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Gotlands Försvarsmuseum	https://www.gotlandsforsvarsmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Grenna museum	http://www.grennamuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Gustavianum	http://www.gustavianum.uu.se
GLAM LIST	Hallands kulturhistoriska museum	https://www.museumhalland.se
GLAM LIST	Hallwylska museet	http://hallwylskamuseet.se
GLAM LIST	Hälsinglands Museum	https://halsinglandsmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Hemslöjden	https://hemslojden.org
GLAM LIST	Historiska museet	http://historiska.se
GLAM LIST	Institutionen för naturgeografi, Stockholms universitet	https://www.natgeo.su.se
GLAM LIST	Jamtli	http://www.jamtli.com
GLAM LIST	Järnvägmuseet	https://www.jarnvagsmuseet.se
GLAM LIST	Jönköpings läns museum	https://jonkopingslansmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Kalmar läns museum	https://www.kalmarlansmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Karlsborgs Fästningsmuseum	https://www.sfv.se/sv/fastigheter/sverige/vastra-gotalands-lan-o/karlsborgs-fastning
GLAM LIST	Köpings museum	https://koping.se/kultur-fritid--turism/kultur/kopings-museum.html
GLAM LIST	Kulturmagasinet	https://kulturmagasinet.helsingborg.se
GLAM LIST	Kungliga biblioteket	https://www.kb.se
GLAM LIST	Länsmuseet Gävleborg	http://www.lansmuseetgavleborg.se
GLAM LIST	Litografiska Museet	http://www.litografiskamuseet.se

GLAM LIST	Livrustkammaren	http://livrustkammaren.se
GLAM LIST	Malmö Museer	https://malmo.se/museer
GLAM LIST	Marinmuseum	https://www.marinmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Medelhavsmuseet	http://www.varldskulturmuseerna.se/medelhavsmuseet
GLAM LIST	Miliseum	https://www.miliseum.com
GLAM LIST	Mölnads stadsmuseum	https://www.molndal.se/molndals-stadsmuseum.html
GLAM LIST	Musikverket	https://musikverket.se
GLAM LIST	Nationalmuseum	https://www.nationalmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Nordiska museet	nordiskamuseet.se
GLAM LIST	Örebro läns museum	https://www.olm.se
GLAM LIST	Östasiatiska museet	http://www.varldskulturmuseerna.se/en/ostasiatiskamuseet
GLAM LIST	Östergötlands museum	http://ostergotlandsmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Österlens museum	http://www.simrishamn.se/sv/kultur_fritid/osterlens_museum
GLAM LIST	Postmuseum	http://www.postmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Regionarkivet för Västra Götalandsregionen och Göteborgs Stad	https://goteborg.se/wps/portal/enhetssida/regionarkivet
GLAM LIST	Riksantikvarieämbetet	https://www.raa.se
GLAM LIST	Riksarkivet	https://riksarkivet.se
GLAM LIST	Sjöhistoriska museet	https://www.sjohistoriska.se
GLAM LIST	Skansen	http://www.skansen.se
GLAM LIST	Skoklosters slott	http://skoklostersslott.se
GLAM LIST	Snus- och Tändsticksmuseum	https://www.snusochtandsticksmuseum.se

GLAM LIST	Sörmlands Museum	https://www.sorlandsmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Spårvägmuseet	http://sparvagsmuseet.sl.se
GLAM LIST	Stadsmuseet i Stockholm	https://stadsmuseet.stockholm.se
GLAM LIST	Statens maritima museer	https://www.maritima.se
GLAM LIST	Sundsvalls museum	https://sundsvall.se/uppleva-och-gora/kultur/kulturmagasinet/besok-oss/sundsvalls-museum
GLAM LIST	Tekniska museet	https://www.tekniskamuseet.se
GLAM LIST	Teleseum	https://teleseum.se
GLAM LIST	Thielska Galleriet	https://www.thielskagalleriet.se
GLAM LIST	Trelleborgs museum	https://www.trelleborg.se/sv/uppleva-gora/kultur/trelleborgs-museum
GLAM LIST	Universitetsbiblioteket, Lunds universitet	http://www.ub.lu.se
GLAM LIST	Upplandsmuseet	http://www.upplandsmuseet.se
GLAM LIST	Uppsala universitetsbibliotek	http://www.ub.uu.se
GLAM LIST	Vänersborgs museum	http://www.vanersborgsmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Världskulturmuseet	http://www.varldskulturmuseerna.se/en/varldskulturmuseet
GLAM LIST	Värmdö kommun	http://www.varmdo.se
GLAM LIST	Värmlands Museum	https://varmlandsmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Vasamuseet	https://www.vasamuseet.se
GLAM LIST	Västergötlands museum	http://vastergotlandsmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Västmanlands läns museum	https://www.vastmanlandslansmuseum.se
GLAM LIST	Vetlanda museum	https://vetlanda.se/artikelarkiv/upplev/gratisutstallningarpavetlandamuseum.5.1d2a7c7616342fe18ec4a80d.html
GLAM LIST	Archiv für Zeitgeschichte,	https://www.afz.ethz.ch

	ETH Zürich	
GLAM LIST	Archiv Ortsgeschichte Wetzikon	https://www.wetzikon.ch/stadtleben/kultur/archiv-ortsgeschichte
GLAM LIST	Archives Cantonales Jurassiennes	https://www.jura.ch/arcj
GLAM LIST	Archives Cantonales Vaudoises	https://www.vd.ch/toutes-les-autorites/archives-cantonales-vaudoises-acv
GLAM LIST	Archives d'Etat de Genève	http://ge.ch/archives
GLAM LIST	Bibliothèque cantonale et universitaire Lausanne BCUL	https://www.bcu-lausanne.ch
GLAM LIST	Bildarchiv der ETH- Bibliothek, ETH Zürich	http://www.library.ethz.ch/de/Ressourcen/Bilder-Fotografien-Grafiken/Bildarchiv
GLAM LIST	Bildarchiv des Schweizerischen Arbeiterhilfswerks (SAH)	https://www.bild-video-ton.ch/bestand/signatur/f_5025
GLAM LIST	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (Musée Bolo)	http://www.bolo.ch
GLAM LIST	Historisches Museum Basel	https://www.hmb.ch
GLAM LIST	Hochschularchiv der ETH Zürich, ETH-Bibliothek	http://www.library.ethz.ch/de/Ressourcen/Archivalien-Dokumentationen/Hochschularchiv-der-ETH-Zuerich
GLAM LIST	Institut universitaire d'histoire de la médecine et de la santé publique	http://www.chuv.ch/ihmsp
GLAM LIST	Kathryn and Shelby Cullom Davis Library (Graduate Institute, Geneva)	http://graduateinstitute.ch
GLAM LIST	Kunstmuseum Appenzell	http://www.kunstmuseumappenzell.ch
GLAM LIST	Kunstmuseum Basel	https://kunstmuseumbasel.ch
GLAM LIST	Le Temps Archives	https://letempsarchives.ch
GLAM LIST	Max Frisch-Archiv (ETH-	https://www.ethz.ch

	Bibliothek Zürich)	
GLAM LIST	Musée de la Chaussure	http://shoemuseum.ch
GLAM LIST	Neuchâtel Herbarium (Université de Neuchâtel)	https://www.unine.ch
GLAM LIST	Rousseau Online (infoclio.ch)	https://www.rousseauonline.ch
GLAM LIST	SBB Historic – Stiftung Historisches Erbe der SBB	https://www.sbbhistoric.ch
GLAM LIST	Schweizerische Stiftung Public Domain	http://www.publicdomain.ch
GLAM LIST	Schweizerischen Nationalbibliothek	https://www.nb.admin.ch
GLAM LIST	Schweizerisches Bundesarchiv	http://www.bar.admin.ch
GLAM LIST	Schweizerisches Nationalmuseum	https://www.nationalmuseum.ch
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv Baden	https://www.baden.chde/leben-wohnen/online-service/online-stadtarchiv.html/267
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv und Kläui Bibliothek, Stadt Uster	https://www.uster.chunterinstanzen/11723
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv Winterthur	https://stadt.winterthur.chgemeinde/verwaltung/stadtkanzlei/stadtarchiv
GLAM LIST	Stadtarchiv Zürich	https://www.stadt-zuerich.chprd/en/index/stadtarchiv.html
GLAM LIST	Stadtbibliothek Schaffhausen	http://www.bibliotheken-schaffhausen.ch
GLAM LIST	Thomas-Mann-Archiv (ETH- Bibliothek Zürich)	http://www.tma.ethz.ch
GLAM LIST	Universitätsbibliothek Basel	https://www.ub.unibas.chub-hauptbibliothek
GLAM LIST	Zentralbibliothek Solothurn	http://www.zbsolothurn.ch
GLAM LIST	Zentralbibliothek Zürich	https://www.zb.uzh.ch

GLAM LIST	國立故宮博物院 (National Palace Museum)	https://www.npm.gov.tw
GLAM LIST	SALT	https://saltonline.org
GLAM LIST	Ashwell Village Museum	http://www.ashwellmuseum.org.uk
GLAM LIST	Bath Postal Museum	http://bathpostalmuseum.org.uk
GLAM LIST	Beith Library	https://www.north-ayrshire.gov.uk/libraries/find-reserve-and-renew-items.aspx
GLAM LIST	Birmingham Museums Trust	http://www.birminghammuseums.org.uk
GLAM LIST	Brackley Town Hall	http://www.brackleynorthants-tc.gov.uk
GLAM LIST	Bradfield Parish Council Offices	https://www.bradfieldparishcouncil.org.uk/
GLAM LIST	Braemar Castle	https://www.braemarcastle.co.uk
GLAM LIST	Brighton Museums	https://brightonmuseums.org.uk
GLAM LIST	British Library	https://www.bl.uk
GLAM LIST	Buxton Museum & Art Gallery	https://derbyshire.gov.uk/leisure/buxton-museum/buxton-museum-and-art-gallery.aspx
GLAM LIST	Captain Cook Birthplace Museum	http://www.captcook-ne.co.uk
GLAM LIST	Carisbrooke Castle Museum	http://carisbrookecastlemuseum.org.uk
GLAM LIST	Coventry Council House	https://www.coventry.gov.uk/directory_record/66/the_council_house
GLAM LIST	Cricklade Town Hall	https://www.crickladetowncouncil.gov.uk
GLAM LIST	Cusworth Hall Museum and Park	https://www.heritagedoncaster.org.uk/cusworth-hall
GLAM LIST	Dereham Assembly Rooms	https://www.derehamtowncouncil.info
GLAM LIST	Doncaster Mansion House	http://www.doncaster.gov.uk/services/culture-leisure-tourism/mansion-house

GLAM LIST	Doncaster Museum and Art Gallery	http://www.doncaster.gov.uk/services/culture-leisure-tourism/doncaster-museum-and-art-gallery
GLAM LIST	Dorman Museum	http://www.dormanmuseum.co.uk
GLAM LIST	East Riding Archives	https://www.eastriding.gov.uk/leisure/archives-family-and-local-history
GLAM LIST	Eden Camp Modern History Theme Museum	http://www.edencamp.co.uk
GLAM LIST	Fraserburgh Library	https://www.aberdeenshire.gov.uk/libraries/locations/local-libraries/fraserburgh-library
GLAM LIST	Fraserburgh Town House	https://artuk.org/visit/venues/fraserburgh-town-house-6563
GLAM LIST	Greater Manchester County Record Office	http://www.gmcro.co.uk
GLAM LIST	Harris Manchester College, University of Oxford	http://www.hmc.ox.ac.uk
GLAM LIST	Hastings Library	https://www.eastsussex.gov.uk/libraries/local/locations/hastings
GLAM LIST	Herbert Art Gallery and Museum	https://www.theherbert.org
GLAM LIST	Holmesdale Natural History Club	http://www.hnhc.co.uk
GLAM LIST	Horniman Museum and Gardens	https://www.horniman.ac.uk
GLAM LIST	Imperial War Museum	http://www.iwm.org.uk
GLAM LIST	Jerwood Gallery	http://jerwoodcollection.online
GLAM LIST	Jerwood Library of the Performing Arts (Trinity Laban)	http://www.trinitylaban.ac.uk/jerwoodlibrary
GLAM LIST	Laurence Sterne Trust	http://www.laurencesternetrust.org.uk
GLAM LIST	Lewes Town Hall	http://www.lewes-tc.gov.uk

GLAM LIST	Llyfrgell Genedlaethol Cymru (National Library of Wales)	https://www.library.wales
GLAM LIST	London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine	https://www.lshtm.ac.uk
GLAM LIST	LSE Library: The British Library of Political and Economic Science	http://www.lse.ac.uk/library
GLAM LIST	Maldon Moot Hall	http://www.themoothall.co.uk
GLAM LIST	Mary Rose Trust	http://www.maryrose.org
GLAM LIST	Middlesbrough Town Hall	https://www.middlesbrough.gov.uk/council-buildings/town-hall
GLAM LIST	Museum of Hartlepool	https://www.facebook.com/museumofhartlepool
GLAM LIST	National Brewery Heritage Trust	http://nationalbreweryheritagetrust.co.uk
GLAM LIST	National Galleries of Scotland	http://www.nationalgalleries.org
GLAM LIST	National Library of Scotland	https://www.nls.uk
GLAM LIST	Natural History Museum	http://www.nhm.ac.uk
GLAM LIST	New College, University of Oxford	https://www.new.ox.ac.uk
GLAM LIST	Newark Town Hall Museum and Art Gallery	http://www.newarktownhallmuseum.co.uk
GLAM LIST	Newcastle Libraries	https://www.newcastle.gov.uk/services/newcastle-libraries-community-hubs
GLAM LIST	Norfolk and Norwich University Hospital	http://www.nnuh.nhs.uk
GLAM LIST	North Ayrshire Heritage Centre	http://www.north-ayrshire.gov.uk
GLAM LIST	Portable Antiquities Scheme	http://finds.org.uk
GLAM LIST	Portico Library and Gallery	https://www.theportico.org.uk

GLAM LIST	Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew	https://www.kew.org
GLAM LIST	Royal Hampshire Regiment Museum	https://www.royalhampshireregiment.org
GLAM LIST	Royal Pump Room	https://www.harrogate.gov.uk/info/20151/royal_pump_room_museum
GLAM LIST	Royal Watercolour Society	https://www.royalwatercoloursociety.co.uk
GLAM LIST	Royston & District Museum & Art Gallery	http://www.roystonmuseum.org.uk
GLAM LIST	Science Museum Group	https://www.sciencemuseumgroup.org.uk
GLAM LIST	Scottish Maritime Museum	https://www.scottishmaritimemuseum.org
GLAM LIST	St Peter's College, University of Oxford	https://www.spc.ox.ac.uk
GLAM LIST	Sudley House (National Museums Liverpool)	https://www.liverpoolmuseums.org.uk/sudley-house
GLAM LIST	Tenby Town Council	https://tenbytowncouncil.co.uk
GLAM LIST	The Hepworth Wakefield	https://hepworthwakefield.org
GLAM LIST	The Laurels	https://historicengland.org.uk/listing/the-list/list-entry/1316517
GLAM LIST	The Tank Museum	https://tankmuseum.org
GLAM LIST	Thirlestane Castle	https://www.thirlestanecastle.co.uk
GLAM LIST	Toynbee Hall	https://www.toynbeehall.org.uk
GLAM LIST	Tyne & Wear Archives & Museums	https://www.twmuseums.org.uk
GLAM LIST	University of Dundee Museum Collections	https://www.dundee.ac.uk/museum
GLAM LIST	University of Edinburgh	https://www.ed.ac.uk
GLAM LIST	University of Manchester	https://www.manchester.ac.uk
GLAM LIST	University of St Andrews	https://www.st-andrews.ac.uk

GLAM LIST	University of Sussex	http://www.sussex.ac.uk
GLAM LIST	University of York	https://www.york.ac.uk/
GLAM LIST	Victoria and Albert Museum	https://www.vam.ac.uk
GLAM LIST	Wellcome Collection	https://wellcomecollection.org
GLAM LIST	York Museums Trust	https://www.yorkmuseumstrust.org.uk
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Comunitaria Paco Espínola	https://www.facebook.com/bibliotecacomunitariapaco.espinola
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca de ACSUN	http://acsunuruguaynegro.blogspot.com
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca del Poder Legislativo	https://biblioteca.parlamento.gub.uy/biblioteca
GLAM LIST	Biblioteca Francisco Schinca	http://bibliotecas.montevideo.gub.uy/bibliotecas/biblioteca-francisco-schinca
GLAM LIST	Centro de Fotografía de Montevideo	http://cdf.montevideo.gub.uy
GLAM LIST	Fundación Felisberto Hernández	http://www.felisberto.org.uy
GLAM LIST	Intendencia de Canelones	https://www.imcanelones.gub.uy
GLAM LIST	Intendencia de Maldonado	http://www.maldonado.uy
GLAM LIST	Museo Nacional de Artes Visuales	http://mnav.gub.uy/cms.php
GLAM LIST	Museo Zorrilla	http://www.museozorrilla.gub.uy
GLAM LIST	Abilene Christian University Library	https://www.acu.edu/library
GLAM LIST	Abilene Library Consortium	https://www.alc.org
GLAM LIST	Abilene Public Library	https://www.abilenetx.gov/apl
GLAM LIST	Alamance County Public Libraries	https://www.alamance-nc.com/library
GLAM LIST	Albright-Knox	https://www.albrightknox.org

GLAM LIST	American Aviation Historical Society	https://www.aahs-online.org
GLAM LIST	American Numismatic Society	http://numismatics.org
GLAM LIST	Anacostia Community Museum	http://anacostia.si.edu
GLAM LIST	Andrews Public Library	http://nantahalalibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Appalachian State University	https://www.appstate.edu
GLAM LIST	Archer Public Library	https://archer.ploud.net
GLAM LIST	Archives of American Art	https://www.aaa.si.edu
GLAM LIST	Art Institute of Chicago	https://www.artic.edu
GLAM LIST	Arthur M. Sackler Gallery	https://asia.si.edu
GLAM LIST	Atlanta Public Library	http://afplweb.com
GLAM LIST	Augusta-Richmond County Public Library	https://arcpls.org
GLAM LIST	Barnes Foundation	https://www.barnesfoundation.org
GLAM LIST	Barton College	https://www.barton.edu
GLAM LIST	Bastrop Public Library	https://bastrop.biblionix.com/catalog
GLAM LIST	Baylor County Free Library	https://www.baylorcountylibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Belmont Abbey College	https://www.belmontabbeycollege.edu
GLAM LIST	Bennett College	https://www.bennett.edu
GLAM LIST	Berkeley Natural History Museums	https://bnhm.berkeley.edu
GLAM LIST	Bicentennial City County Library	https://www.paducahtxlibrary.com
GLAM LIST	Birmingham Museum of Art	https://www.artsbma.org
GLAM LIST	Bonham Public Library	http://www.bonhamlibrary.net

GLAM LIST	Boonville Community Public Library	https://nwrlibrary.org/boonville
GLAM LIST	Boston Public Library	https://www.bpl.org
GLAM LIST	Bowdoin College Museum of Art	http://www.bowdoin.edu/art-museum
GLAM LIST	Bowie Public Library	https://www.bowiepubliclibrary.com
GLAM LIST	Boyce Ditto Public Library	https://www.mineralwellstx.gov/98/Library
GLAM LIST	Braswell Memorial Library	https://braswell-library.libguides.com
GLAM LIST	Brevard College	https://brevard.edu
GLAM LIST	Brevard Music Center	https://www.brevardmusic.org
GLAM LIST	Brooklyn Museum	https://www.brooklynmuseum.org
GLAM LIST	Burke County Public Library	http://bcpls.org
GLAM LIST	Cabarrus County Public Library	https://cabarruscounty.us/departments/library
GLAM LIST	Calhoun-Gordon County Library	https://ngri.org/locations/calhoun-gordon
GLAM LIST	California Historical Society	https://www.californiahistoricalsociety.org
GLAM LIST	California State University, Fresno	http://www.fresnostate.edu/artshum/armenianstudies
GLAM LIST	Camden Public Library	http://camden.lib.me.us
GLAM LIST	Campbell University	https://www.campbell.edu
GLAM LIST	Carnegie Hall Archives	https://www.carnegiehall.org
GLAM LIST	Carolinas Aviation Museum	https://www.carolinasaviation.org
GLAM LIST	Carrollton Public Library	https://www.cityofcarrollton.com/departments/departments-g-p/library
GLAM LIST	Catawba County Library	http://www.catawbacountync.gov/county-services/library
GLAM LIST	Catawba County Library	http://www.catawbacounty.org/resources/Librar

		y.html
GLAM LIST	Center for Jewish History	http://www.cjh.org
GLAM LIST	Central Piedmont Community College	https://www.cpcc.edu
GLAM LIST	Chapel Hill Historical Society	https://chapelhillhistoricalsociety.org
GLAM LIST	Charlotte Mecklenburg Library	https://www.cmlibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Chattahoochee Valley Regional Library System	https://www.cvlga.org
GLAM LIST	Chowan University	https://www.chowan.edu
GLAM LIST	City of Raleigh Museum	https://raleighnc.gov/places/city-raleigh-museum
GLAM LIST	Clark Art Institute	https://www.clarkart.edu
GLAM LIST	Clarksville-Habersham Library	https://clarksvillelibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Cleveland County Memorial Library	https://ccml.org/ccml
GLAM LIST	Cleveland Museum of Art	http://www.clevelandart.org
GLAM LIST	Coleman Public Library	http://www.cityofcolemantx.us/library/facilities/index.html
GLAM LIST	Columbus Public Library (Columbus, Ga.)	https://www.cvlga.org/columbus-public-library
GLAM LIST	Comanche Public Library	https://www.comanchepubliclibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Cooke County Library	https://cookecountylibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Cooper-Hewitt, National Design Museum	https://www.cooperhewitt.org
GLAM LIST	Cornell University Library	https://www.library.cornell.edu
GLAM LIST	Cuero Public Library	https://www.cityofcuero.com/186/Library

GLAM LIST	Cumberland County Public Library	https://www.co.cumberland.nc.us/departments/library
GLAM LIST	Danbury Public Library	http://danburylibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Davidson College	https://www.davidson.edu
GLAM LIST	Davidson County Public Library System	https://davidson.nccardinal.org/eg/opac/home
GLAM LIST	Davie County Public Library	https://www.daviecountync.gov/896/Public-Library
GLAM LIST	Davison Art Center, Wesleyan University	http://www.wesleyan.edu/dac
GLAM LIST	DC Public Library	http://dclibrary.org/research/collections
GLAM LIST	Deaf Smith County Library	https://www.deafsmithcolib.org
GLAM LIST	Delta County Public Library	https://deltalibraries.org
GLAM LIST	Denton Public Library	https://library.cityofdenton.com
GLAM LIST	Detroit Institute of Arts	https://www.dia.org
GLAM LIST	Digital Library of Georgia	https://dlg.usg.edu
GLAM LIST	Dublin Public Library	https://www.dublinlibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Duke University	https://www.duke.edu
GLAM LIST	Duke University Libraries	https://library.duke.edu
GLAM LIST	Duke University Libraries	https://library.duke.edu
GLAM LIST	Durham County Library	https://durhamcountylibrary.org
GLAM LIST	East Bend Public Library	https://nwrlibrary.org/eastbend
GLAM LIST	East Carolina University	https://www.ecu.edu
GLAM LIST	Ed & Hazel Richmond Public Library	https://aptx.gov/208/Library
GLAM LIST	Edgecombe Community College	https://www.edgecombe.edu

GLAM LIST	Edgecombe County Memorial Library	https://edgecombelibrary.libguides.com
GLAM LIST	Electra Public Library	https://www.electrapubliclibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Elizabeth City State University	https://www.ecsu.edu
GLAM LIST	Elkin Public Library	https://nwrlibrary.org/elkin
GLAM LIST	Elon University	https://www.elon.edu
GLAM LIST	Ernst Mayr Library of the Museum of Comparative Zoology	https://library.mcz.harvard.edu
GLAM LIST	Farmville Public Library	https://www.farmvillelibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Fayetteville State University	https://www.uncfsu.edu
GLAM LIST	Ferris Public Library	https://ferris.ploud.net
GLAM LIST	Field Museum Library	http://fieldmuseum.org
GLAM LIST	Folger Shakespeare Library	https://www.folger.edu
GLAM LIST	Forsyth County Public Library	https://www.forsythpl.org
GLAM LIST	Fort Worth Public Library	https://www.fortworthgov.org/Library
GLAM LIST	Freer Gallery of Art	https://asia.si.edu
GLAM LIST	Friench Simpson Memorial Library	https://hallettsvillelibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Friends of Oaxacan Folk Art (FOFA)	https://www.fofa.us
GLAM LIST	Gaines County Library	https://www.gainescountylibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Gardner-Webb University	https://gardner-webb.edu
GLAM LIST	Gaston College	https://www.gaston.edu
GLAM LIST	Geographicus	https://www.geographicus.com
GLAM LIST	George Eastman Museum	https://www.eastman.org

GLAM LIST	George Washington University	https://www.gwu.edu
GLAM LIST	Gerald R. Ford Presidential Library and Museum	https://www.fordlibrarymuseum.gov
GLAM LIST	Gibbs Memorial Library	https://www.gibbslibrarymexia.org
GLAM LIST	Graham County Public Library	https://ghcopublib.org
GLAM LIST	Grand Rapids Public Museum	https://www.grpm.org
GLAM LIST	Granville County Public Library	https://granville.lib.nc.us
GLAM LIST	Greensboro College	https://www.greensboro.edu
GLAM LIST	Greensboro History Museum	https://greensborohistory.org
GLAM LIST	Greensboro Public Library	https://library.greensboro-nc.gov
GLAM LIST	Guilford College	https://www.guilford.edu
GLAM LIST	Hall County Library System (Ga.)	https://www.hallcountylibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Harnett County Public Library	https://harnett.libguides.com/hcpl
GLAM LIST	Harvard Library	https://library.harvard.edu/digital-collections
GLAM LIST	Haywood County Public Library	https://haywoodlibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Hemphill County Library	https://harringtonlc.org/canadian
GLAM LIST	Henderson County Public Library	https://www.hendersoncountync.gov/library
GLAM LIST	Hickory Public Library	https://www.hickorync.gov/library
GLAM LIST	Higgins Public Library	https://www.higginslibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Hirshhorn Museum and Sculpture Garden	https://hirshhorn.si.edu

GLAM LIST	Hondo Public Library	https://hondo-tx.org/library
GLAM LIST	Houston County Public Library	https://houpl.org
GLAM LIST	Indiana Historical Society	https://indianahistory.org
GLAM LIST	Indiana Historical Society	https://indianahistory.org
GLAM LIST	Indiana State Library and Historical Bureau	https://www.in.gov/library
GLAM LIST	Indianapolis Museum of Art at Newfields	https://discovernewfields.org
GLAM LIST	J. Paul Getty Trust	http://www.getty.edu
GLAM LIST	Jacksonville Public Library	https://jaxpubliclibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Jewish Historical Society of the Upper Midwest	http://www.jhsum.org
GLAM LIST	Jewish Women's Archive	http://jwa.org
GLAM LIST	Johnson C. Smith University	http://www.jcsu.edu
GLAM LIST	Johnson C. Smith University	https://www.jcsu.edu
GLAM LIST	Keene Public Library and the Historical Society of Cheshire County	https://ci.keene.nh.us/keene-public-library
GLAM LIST	Kings Mountain Historical Museum	https://www.kingsmountainmuseum.org
GLAM LIST	Lampasas Public Library	https://www.lampasas.org/252/Library
GLAM LIST	Lena Armstrong Public Library	https://belton.biblionix.com/catalog
GLAM LIST	Levine Museum of the New South	http://www.museumofthenewsouth.org
GLAM LIST	Liberty Public Library	https://www.libertypubliclibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Library Company of Philadelphia	http://www.librarycompany.org

GLAM LIST	Library of Congress	https://www.loc.gov
GLAM LIST	Library of Virginia	http://www.lva.virginia.gov
GLAM LIST	Livingston Municipal Library	https://www.livingstonlibrary.net
GLAM LIST	Los Angeles County Museum of Art	http://www.lacma.org
GLAM LIST	Louisburg College	https://www.louisburg.edu
GLAM LIST	Lucy Hill Patterson Memorial Library	https://www.rockdalelibrarytx.org
GLAM LIST	MBLWHOI Library	http://www.mblwhoilibrary.org
GLAM LIST	McDowell County Public Library	https://mcdowellpubliclibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Mennonite Church USA Archives	http://www.mcusa-archives.org
GLAM LIST	Meredith College	https://www.meredith.edu
GLAM LIST	Meridian Public Library	https://www.mld.org
GLAM LIST	Mesquite Public Library	https://www.cityofmesquite.com/454/Library
GLAM LIST	Methodist University	https://www.methodist.edu
GLAM LIST	Metropolitan Museum of Art	https://www.metmuseum.org
GLAM LIST	Miami University Libraries	http://digital.lib.muohio.edu
GLAM LIST	Middle Georgia Archives	https://www.mga.edu/library/archives/index.php
GLAM LIST	Mineola Memorial Library	https://mineola.ploud.net
GLAM LIST	Minneapolis Institute of Art	https://new.artsmia.org
GLAM LIST	Missouri Botanical Garden, Peter H. Raven Library	http://www.missouribotanicalgarden.orgplant-science/plant-science/resources/raven-library.aspx
GLAM LIST	Mitchell Community College	https://mitchellcc.edu
GLAM LIST	Montgomery County Memorial Library	https://countylibrary.org

GLAM LIST	Montreat College	https://www.montreat.edu
GLAM LIST	Mount Airy Museum of Regional History	http://www.northcarolinamuseum.org
GLAM LIST	Mount Airy Public Library	https://nwrlibrary.org/mountairy
GLAM LIST	Museum of the Albemarle	https://www.museumofthealbemarle.com
GLAM LIST	NASA	https://www.nasa.gov
GLAM LIST	National Air and Space Museum	https://airandspace.si.edu
GLAM LIST	National Archives and Records Administration	https://www.archives.gov
GLAM LIST	National Gallery of Art	https://www.nga.gov
GLAM LIST	National Library of Medicine	http://www.nlm.nih.gov
GLAM LIST	National Museum of African American History and Culture	https://nmaahc.si.edu
GLAM LIST	National Museum of African Art	https://africa.si.edu
GLAM LIST	National Museum of Natural History	http://naturalhistory.si.edu
GLAM LIST	National Museum of the American Indian	https://americanindian.si.edu
GLAM LIST	National Portrait Gallery	https://npg.si.edu
GLAM LIST	National Postal Museum	https://postalmuseum.si.edu
GLAM LIST	Nellie Pederson Civic Library	https://www.cliftonlib.com
GLAM LIST	Nesbitt Memorial Library	https://www.columbustexaslibrary.net
GLAM LIST	Neuse Regional Library	https://www.neuselibrary.org
GLAM LIST	New Bern-Craven County Public Library	http://newbern.cpclub.org

GLAM LIST	New York Botanical Garden, LuEsther T. Mertz Library	http://mertzdigital.nybg.org
GLAM LIST	New York Public Library	https://www.nypl.org
GLAM LIST	Newberry Library	https://www.newberry.org
GLAM LIST	North Carolina Agricultural and Technical State University	https://www.ncat.edu
GLAM LIST	North Carolina Central University	https://www.nccu.edu
GLAM LIST	North Carolina Humanities Council	https://nchumanities.org
GLAM LIST	North Carolina Wesleyan College	https://ncwc.edu
GLAM LIST	Northeast Georgia Regional Library System	https://negeorgialibraries.org
GLAM LIST	Olivia Raney Local History Library	https://www.wakegov.com/departments-government/libraries/locations/olivia-raney-local-history-library
GLAM LIST	Orange County Historical Museum	https://www.thehistorycenter.org
GLAM LIST	Oregon State University Special Collections & Archives	http://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu
GLAM LIST	Outer Banks History Center	https://archives.ncdcr.gov/researchers/outer-banks-history-center
GLAM LIST	Palacios Library	https://www.palacioslibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Paleontological Research Institution	http://www.digitalatlasofancientlife.org
GLAM LIST	Palestine Public Library	http://www1.youseemore.com/palestine
GLAM LIST	Park County Local History Digital Archive, Colorado	https://pclha.cvlcollections.org
GLAM LIST	Pasquotank County Library	https://pasquotanklibrary.org

GLAM LIST	Pender County Public Library	https://penderpubliclibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Penland School of Craft	https://penland.org
GLAM LIST	Pine River Library	https://prlibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Queens University of Charlotte	https://www.queens.edu
GLAM LIST	Randolph County Public Library	https://www.randolphlibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Red River County Public Library	http://rrlibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Research Labs of Archaeology (UNC-CH)	https://archaeology.sites.unc.edu
GLAM LIST	Reynolda House Museum of American Art	https://www.reynoldahouse.org
GLAM LIST	Rhode Island School of Design Museum	https://risdmuseum.org
GLAM LIST	Robersonville Public Library	https://bhmlib.org/robersonville
GLAM LIST	Rockingham Community College	https://www.rockinghamcc.edu
GLAM LIST	Rockingham County Public Library	http://www.rcpl.org
GLAM LIST	Rosenberg Library	https://rosenberg-library.org
GLAM LIST	Rowan Public Library	https://www.rowancountync.gov/307/Library
GLAM LIST	Saint Louis Art Museum	https://www.slam.org
GLAM LIST	Saint Mary's School	https://www.sms.edu
GLAM LIST	Salem Academy and College	https://www.salem.edu
GLAM LIST	Sammy Brown Library	https://www.carthagetexas.us/facilities/sammy-brown-library
GLAM LIST	San Diego Air and Space	http://sandiegoairandspace.org

	Museum	
GLAM LIST	Sandhills Community College	https://www.sandhills.edu
GLAM LIST	Schlesinger Library	http://www.radcliffe.edu/schlesinger_library.aspx
GLAM LIST	Schulenburg Public Library	https://www.schulenburglibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Science History Institute	https://www.sciencehistory.org
GLAM LIST	Screven-Jenkins Regional Library System	http://www.sjrls.org
GLAM LIST	Shaw University	https://www.shawu.edu
GLAM LIST	Singletary Memorial Library	https://librarytechnology.org/library/24534
GLAM LIST	Sinton Public Library	https://www.sintontexas.org/2170/Library
GLAM LIST	Smithsonian American Art Museum	https://americanart.si.edu
GLAM LIST	Smithsonian Gardens	https://gardens.si.edu
GLAM LIST	Smithsonian Institution Archives	https://siarchives.si.edu
GLAM LIST	Smithsonian Institution Libraries	https://library.si.edu
GLAM LIST	Smithville Public Library	https://www.smithvillepubliclibrary.org
GLAM LIST	South Dakota State University	https://www.sdstate.edu
GLAM LIST	South Piedmont Community College	https://spcc.edu
GLAM LIST	Southern Methodist University	https://www.smu.edu
GLAM LIST	Southwest Georgia Regional Library	https://www.swgrl.org
GLAM LIST	Southwestern University	https://www.southwestern.edu

GLAM LIST	St. Andrews University	https://www.sa.edu
GLAM LIST	St. Edward's University	https://www.stedwards.edu
GLAM LIST	Stamford Carnegie Library	https://stamford-carnegie.ploud.net
GLAM LIST	Stanly County Museum	http://stanlycountymuseum.com
GLAM LIST	State Library & Archives of Florida	https://www.floridamemory.com
GLAM LIST	State Library of Ohio	https://library.ohio.gov
GLAM LIST	Stephenville Public Library	https://www.stephenvilletx.gov/parks-leisure/page/library
GLAM LIST	Stonewall County Library	https://www.stonewall-library.com
GLAM LIST	Surry Community College	https://www.surry.edu
GLAM LIST	Swannanoa Valley Museum and History Center	https://www.history.swannanoavalleymuseum.org
GLAM LIST	Swisher County Library	https://www.swishercolib.org
GLAM LIST	Taft Public Library	http://www.taftpubliclibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Tarleton State University	https://www.tarleton.edu
GLAM LIST	Texas State University	http://www.txstate.edu
GLAM LIST	Texas Wesleyan University	https://txwes.edu
GLAM LIST	The Forest History Society	https://foresthistor.org
GLAM LIST	The Grand Lodge of Ancient, Free and Accepted Masons of North Carolina	https://www.grandlodge-nc.org
GLAM LIST	Timpson Public Library	https://librarytechnology.org/library/193573
GLAM LIST	Transylvania County Library	https://library.transylvaniacounty.org
GLAM LIST	Tyrrell Historical Library	http://tyrrellhistoricallibrary.contentdm.oclc.org/cdm
GLAM LIST	U.S. Department of Agriculture, National	https://www.nal.usda.gov

	Agricultural Library	
GLAM LIST	UC Berkeley (Department of Geography)	https://geography.berkeley.edu
GLAM LIST	UMass Amherst Libraries	https://www.library.umass.edu
GLAM LIST	Union County Public Library	https://www.unioncountync.gov/departments/library
GLAM LIST	University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	https://www.unc.edu
GLAM LIST	University of North Carolina at Charlotte	https://www.uncc.edu
GLAM LIST	University of North Carolina at Greensboro	https://www.uncg.edu
GLAM LIST	University of North Carolina at Pembroke	https://www.uncp.edu
GLAM LIST	University of South Dakota	https://www.usd.edu
GLAM LIST	University of Texas at El Paso	https://www.utep.edu
GLAM LIST	University of Washington Libraries Digital Collections	http://content.lib.washington.edu
GLAM LIST	Upper Arlington Public Library.	http://www.uaarchives.org/
GLAM LIST	USDA National Wildlife Research Center	https://www.aphis.usda.gov/aphis/ourfocus/wildlifedamage/programs/nwrc
GLAM LIST	Van Zandt County Library	https://www.vanzandtlibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Virginia Commonwealth University Libraries	http://www.library.vcu.edu
GLAM LIST	Wake County Public Libraries	https://catalog.wakegov.com
GLAM LIST	Wake Forest University	https://www.wfu.edu
GLAM LIST	Walters Art Museum	https://thewalters.org

GLAM LIST	Warren County Memorial Library	http://www.wcmlibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Washington Memorial Library (Macon, Ga.)	http://biblib.org/locations/washington-memorial-library
GLAM LIST	Watauga County Public Library	https://www.arlibrary.org/watauga
GLAM LIST	West Public Library	https://www.westpl.org
GLAM LIST	Western Carolina University	https://www.wcu.edu
GLAM LIST	Western Science Center	https://www.westernsciencecenter.org
GLAM LIST	Wharton County Library	http://www.whartonco.lib.tx.us
GLAM LIST	William Peace University	https://peace.edu
GLAM LIST	Wilson County Public Library	https://www.wilsoncountypubliclibrary.org
GLAM LIST	Wingate University	https://www.wingate.edu
GLAM LIST	Woodrow Wilson Presidential Library	http://www.woodrowwilson.org
GLAM LIST	Yadkin County Public Library	https://nwrlibrary.org/yadkin
GLAM LIST	Yale Center for British Art	https://britishart.yale.edu
GLAM LIST	Yale University Art Gallery	https://artgallery.yale.edu
GLAM LIST	Yale University Library	https://web.library.yale.edu
GLAM LIST	Colección Amadeo León	https://fotoleonbocono.tumblr.com

Contemporary art and art market	Hyperallergic	https://hyperallergic.com/
Contemporary art and art market	Flash Art	https://flash---art.com/
Contemporary art and art market	Artforum	www.artforum.com

Contemporary art and art market	Documenta	https://www.documenta.de/#
Contemporary art and art market	Frieze	https://www.frieze.com/
Contemporary art and art market	Art Parma Fair	https://www.artparmafair.it/
Contemporary art and art market	Art Basel	https://www.artbasel.com/
Contemporary art and art market	Artefiera	www.artefiera.it
Contemporary art and art market	e-flux	https://www.e-flux.com/journal/
Contemporary art and art market	Artribune	https://www.artribune.com/
Contemporary art and art market	Christies	https://www.christies.com/
Contemporary art and art market	Sothebys	https://www.sothebys.com/en/
Open Access Journal	Collection & curation	https://www.emerald.com/insight/publication/issn/2514-9326
Open Access Journal	Il Capitale Culturale	http://riviste.unimc.it/index.php/cap-cult/index
Open Access Journal	Cultura Anthropology	https://journal.culanth.org/index.php/ca
Open Access Journal	Culture Unbound	https://cultureunbound.ep.liu.se/
Open Access Journal	Game Studies	http://gamestudies.org/2003
Open Access Journal	Creativity	http://www.creativity.uwb.edu.pl/index.php/en/
Open Access Journal	Virtual Archeology	https://polipapers.upv.es/index.php/var
Open Access Journal	Science and Technology of Archaeological Research	https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/ysta20
Open Access Journal	Heritage Science	https://heritagesciencejournal.springeropen.com/

Open Access Journal	Open Archeology	https://www.degruyter.com/view/journals/opar/0par-overview.xml
Open Access Journal	Studia Antiqua et Archaeologica	http://saa.uaic.ro/
Open Access Journal	GRBS	https://grbs.library.duke.edu/
Open Access Journal	Anuario Musical	http://anuariomusical.revistas.csic.es/index.php/anuariomusical
Open Access Journal	JSTA	http://artes.ucp.pt/citarj/
Open Access Journal	Arte, Individuo e Sociedad	https://revistas.ucm.es/index.php/ARIS
Open Access Journal	Spatium	https://spatium.rs/index.php/home/issue/view/2
Open Access Journal	Revista180	http://www.revista180.udp.cl/index.php/revista180
Open Access Journal	EGA	https://polipapers.upv.es/index.php/EGA/index
Open Access Journal	Journal of Aesthetics & Culture	https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/zjac20/current
Open Access Journal	Estetika	https://estetikajournal.org/
Open Access Journal	Artnodes	https://www.raco.cat/index.php/Artnodes
Open Access Journal	Aisthesis	https://oajournals.fupress.net/index.php/aisthesis
Open Access Journal	Ars Longa	https://ojs.uv.es/index.php/arslonga
Open Access Journal	Revue de l'art	http://www.centrechastel.paris-sorbonne.fr/page/revue-de-lart-0
Open Access Journal	Film Criticism	https://www.filmcriticismjournal.org/
Open Access Journal	LAA	https://llufb.llu.lv/Raksti/Landscape_Architecture_Art/
Movie Festivals		https://filmfreeway.com/NEWYORKCITYINTERNATIONALFILMFESTIVALNYCIFF
Movie Festivals		https://www.bcnfilmfest.com/en

Movie Festivals		https://www.berlinale.de/en/home.html
Movie Festivals		https://www.europa-cinemas.org/en
Movie Festivals		https://tiff.net/
Movie Festivals		www.torinofilmfest.org
Movie Festivals		https://www.locarnofestival.ch/LFF/home.html
Movie Festivals		https://www.screendaily.com/
Movie Festivals		https://www.labiennale.org/it/cinema/2021
Movie Festivals		https://iffr.com/en
Movie Festivals		https://www.annecy.org/home
Movie Festivals		https://www.kviff.com/en/homepage
Movie Festivals		https://www.sff.ba/
Movie Festivals		https://www.sansebastianfestival.com/in/
Movie Festivals		https://poff.ee/en/
Movie Festivals		https://americanfilmmarket.com/
Movie Festivals		https://www.sundance.org/
Movie Festivals		https://www.sxsw.com/
Movie Festivals		https://tribecafilm.com/
Movie Festivals		https://www.londonfilmandcomiccon.com/
Movie Festivals		https://www.bfi.org.uk/
Movie Festivals		https://glasgowfilm.org/glasgow-film-festival
Movie Festivals		www.eif.co.uk/
Movie Festivals		https://sheffdocfest.com/
Movie Festivals		https://www.biff.kr/eng/

Movie Festivals		https://www.hk.artsfestival.org/en/
Movie Festivals		dubaifilmfest.com
Movie Festivals		https://www.haifaff.co.il/eng
Movie Festivals		https://jff.org.il/en
Movie Festivals		https://www.antalyaff.com/en/
Movie Festivals		https://www.telluridefilmfestival.org/
Lit-journas/blog		https://issuu.com/axolotrivista
Lit-journas/blog		http://www.drogamagazine.com/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.gliepicurei.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://ilproblemadigrendel.net/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.micorrizelitlab.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.bomarsce.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.vocidallisola.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.zestletteraturasostenibile.com/
Lit-journas/blog		https://suiteitalianalt.blogspot.com/
Lit-journas/blog		https://speculariarivista.com/
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Lit-journas/blog		https://antinomie.it/
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Lit-journas/blog		https://www.crackrivista.it/

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Lit-journas/blog		https://formicaleone.com/
Lit-journas/blog		http://fantastico.pro/
Lit-journas/blog		https://lagrandestinzione.wordpress.com/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.lightmagazine.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.lopsiconauta.com/
Lit-journas/blog		https://malgradolemosche.com/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.pidgin.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.radiobusta.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.rivistablam.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://salmuria.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://vocedelverborivista.com/
Lit-journas/blog		http://www.aidainformazioni.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://bombacarta.com/
Lit-journas/blog		http://www.clubautori.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://oajournals.fupress.net/index.php/cromohs/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.fillide.it/
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Lit-journas/blog		https://griseldaonline.unibo.it/
Lit-journas/blog		http://www.horror.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.rivistawaste.com/

Lit-journas/blog		www.irrequieto.eu
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.librinews.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.masedomani.com/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.mattatoio5.com/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.paginatre.it/online/
Lit-journas/blog		http://www.parol.it/
Lit-journas/blog		https://www.psicologiadeisogni.com/
Lit-journas/blog		http://lespleen.eu/
Lit-journas/blog		http://www.spolia.it/online/it/index.htm
Lit-journas/blog		http://www.osservatorioletterario.net/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.armadillofurioso.it/teatro/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.ateatro.it/webzine/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.corrieredellospettacolo.com/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.doppiozero.com/category/tag-universali-area-tematica/teatro
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.dramma.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://drammaturgia.fupress.net/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://fattiditeatro.wordpress.com/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.gufetto.press/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.hystrio.it/
Performances/teathre/		http://www.ilpickwick.it/

critics		
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.iltamburodikattrin.com/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.klpteatro.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.rumorscena.com/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.scenecontemporanee.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.inscenaonlineteam.net/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://sipario.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.saltinaria.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://bandettini.blogautore.repubblica.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.quartaparetepress.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://teatro.persinsala.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.teatrocarcere.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.teatroecritica.net/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.teatrionline.com/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.stratagemmi.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://art-o.net/2008/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.ateatro.it/webzine/

Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.cultureteatrali.org/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.teatroestoria.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.criticiditeatro.it/category/in-primo-piano/le-testate-di-critica-teatrale-sulla-rete/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.altrevelocita.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.artribune.com/category/arti-performative/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://francescadesanctis.wordpress.com/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://boblog.corrieredibologna.corriere.it/author/massimo.marino/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://delteatro.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.eolo-ragazzi.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://incertezzacreativa.wordpress.com/
Performances/teathre/ critics		http://www.culturalife.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://www.linkiesta.it/blog/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://mediamondo.blog/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://teatro.persinsala.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://quantescene-ilpiccolo.blogautore.repubblica.it/
Performances/teathre/ critics		https://grazianograziani.wordpress.com/

Performances/theatre/ critics		https://www.glistatigenerali.com/
Comics		https://www.fumettologica.it/
Comics		https://www.giornalepop.it/
Comics		http://www.fumodichina.com/
Comics		https://nientedadire.it/
Comics		http://europeanclassiccomic.blogspot.com/
Comics		http://europeanbestcomics.blogspot.com/
Comics		http://www.europecomics.com/
Comics		http://bado-badosblog.blogspot.com/2016/05/comics-around-world-european-comics.html
Comics		https://www.goodreads.com/list/show/16413.Best_European_Graphic_Novels_Comics
Comics		https://www.lospaziobianco.it/
Museum	Holocaust Museum	https://collections.ushmm.org/search/
Museum		https://www.mentalfloss.com
Museum		https://www.guggenheim.org/
Museum		https://www.khm.at/
Museum		https://www.rijksmuseum.nl/en
Museum		https://www.britishmuseum.org/
Museum		https://www.louvre.fr/en
Museum		https://www.musee-orsay.fr/en/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/glastonbury-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/tomorrowland/

Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/mad-cool-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/afro-nation/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/rolling-loud-europe/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/primavera-sound/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/isle-of-wight-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/ultra-europe/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/sziget-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/sziget-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/exit-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/download-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/sziget-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/download-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/reading-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/leeds-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/rock-am-ring/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/super-bock-super-rock/

Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/ultra-europe/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/untold-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/mysteryland/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/airbeat-one-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/balaton-sound/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/barcelona-beach-festival/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/electric-love/
Music		https://www.festicket.com/it/festivals/amf-amsterdam-music-festival/
Music		https://www accuradio.com/classical/
Music		https://classical-music-online.net/
Music		https://www.yourclassical.org/listen/radio
Music		https://www.wqxr.org/
Music		https://www.folkalley.com/album-review
Music		https://pitchfork.com/reviews/albums/
Music		https://www.metacritic.com/music
Music		https://www.rollingstone.com/music/music-album-reviews/
Music		https://www.nme.com/reviews/album
Music		http://musicreviews2p0.altervista.org/
Music		https://www.albumoftheyear.org/
Music		https://choice.npr.org/

Music		https://www.dailymusicroll.com/
Music		https://www.metacritic.com/

List's name	Twitter account
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/bibliovaticana
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/bne_biblioteca
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/BiblioNationala
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/bncfirenze
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/bnc_roma
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/bn_org_pl
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/laBnF
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/bnluxembourg
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/MaltaLibraries
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/britishlibrary
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/DetKglBibliotek
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/DNB_Aktuelles
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/NatLibFi
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/kb_nederland
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/kbrbe
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/kungbib
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/LNB_lv
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/NLIreland?ref_src=twsrc%5Egoogle%7Ctwcamp%5Eserp%7Ctwgr%5Eauthor
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/TCKulturTurizm
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/NSK_Zagreb

National Libraries	https://twitter.com/nubskedumk
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/knjiznicanuk
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/narodniknihovna
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/search?q=nasjonalbiblioteket
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/nemzetikonyvtar
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/chnatbib
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/SNK_Martin
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/nbsrb
National Libraries	
National Libraries	
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/PresidentialLib
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/Leninka_ru
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/NLR_library
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/NatLibArm
National Libraries	https://twitter.com/nplgofficial
Archives	https://twitter.com/BBCArchive
Archives	https://twitter.com/staatsarchiv
Archives	
Archives	https://twitter.com/Cinematikbe/
Archives	https://twitter.com/BG_Archives
Archives	
Archives	
Archives	https://twitter.com/Rigsarkivet
Archives	https://twitter.com/rahvusarhiiv
Archives	https://twitter.com/Kansallisarkist
Archives	https://twitter.com/Inafr_officiel
Archives	https://twitter.com/ArchivesnatFr
Archives	https://twitter.com/bundesarchivd
Archives	https://twitter.com/bauhausarchiv
Archives	

Archives	
Archives	https://twitter.com/RTEArchives
Archives	https://twitter.com/NARireland
Archives	
Archives	https://twitter.com/ArchivioLuce
Archives	https://twitter.com/LNarhivs
Archives	
Archives	https://twitter.com/archyvarotarnyb
Archives	
Archives	https://twitter.com/Malta_Archives
Archives	https://twitter.com/BeeldenGeluid
Archives	https://twitter.com/NLNatArchief
Archives	https://twitter.com/Arkivverket
Archives	https://twitter.com/finagovpl
Fashion GLAMs	@Catwalkpictures
Fashion GLAMs	@MoMuAntwerp
Fashion GLAMs	@PalaisGalliera
Fashion GLAMs	@FILAMuseum
Fashion GLAMs	@cerratelli
Fashion GLAMs	@ITSplatform
Fashion GLAMs	@museodeltessuto
Fashion GLAMs	@Modemuze
Fashion GLAMs	@TextielMuseum
Fashion GLAMs	@TRCLEiden
Fashion GLAMs	@MuseodelTraje
Fashion GLAMs	@museobalenciaga
Fashion GLAMs	@Fashion_Museum
Fashion GLAMs	@FashionTextile
Fashion GLAMs	@mensweararchive
Archeological sites	https://twitter.com/parcocolosseo
Archeological sites	https://twitter.com/EH_Stonehenge
Archeological sites	https://twitter.com/pontdugard
Archeological sites	https://twitter.com/RomanBathsBath
Archeological sites	https://twitter.com/newgrangeknowth

Archeological sites	https://twitter.com/ArenesdeNimes
Archeological sites	https://twitter.com/parcodeitempli
Archeological sites	https://twitter.com/delphimuseum
Archeological sites	https://twitter.com/museucoa
Archeological sites	https://twitter.com/pompeii_sites
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/AlbTheater
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/LTheater_linz
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/TheatreDeLiege?lang=fr
National Theaters	http://twitter.com/hnkzgb
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/Cinohra_ND
National Theaters	http://twitter.com/ThocOfficial
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/SKTeatteri?lang=fi
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/CDNnancy
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/TheatreOdeon
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/MarjanishviliTh
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/DT_Berlin
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/NTNGreece
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/TeatroDueParma
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/TeatroKoreja
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/homonovus
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/LesTheatresVDL
National Theaters	Twitter: http://twitter.com/teatrumalta?lang=en
National Theaters	http://www.twitter.com/detnorsketeatre
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/TeatrOpole
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/tnsj
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/NPBGD
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/jdpbgd?lang=en
National Theaters	https://www.twitter.com/presernovo
National Theaters	https://twitter.com/Gbg_Stadsteater
National Theaters	http://twitter.com/toneelmakerij

List's name	Facebook Account
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/BBCArchive
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/oesterreichischesstaatsarchiv/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/rijksarchief
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/CINEMATEK.be/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/BulgarianArchives
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/Hrvatski-dr%C5%BEavni-arhiv-HDA-124359250912928
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/NarodniFilmovyArchiv/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/Rigsarkivetdk
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/rahvusarhiiv
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/Kansallisarkisto/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/Ina.fr/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/Archives.nationales.France
Archives	
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/bauhausarchiv
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/tainiothikigr
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/MNLOrszagosLeveltara
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/rtearchives
Archives	
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/archiviocentrale
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/ArchivioStoricoCinecittaluce/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/LNarhivs

Archives	https://www.facebook.com/lietuvoscentrinisvalstybesar chyvas/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/LVNArchyvas/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/Archives.nationales.Luxemb ourg/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/NationalArchivesMalta/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/beeldengeluid
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/nationaalarchief/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/Arkivverket/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/FINAFilmotekaNarodowaln s tyutAudiowizualny/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/narodowe.archiwum.cyfrow e/
Archives	
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/Arhivele.Nationale.ale.Rom aniei/
Archives	
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/Zgodovinski-arhiv-Ljubljana- 249826845190575/
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/PortalArchivosEspanolesPA RES
Archives	
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/riksarkivet.se
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/Cinemathequesuisse
Archives	https://www.facebook.com/Bundesarchiv.Schweiz
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/pages/Biblioteca%20apostol ica%20vaticana/106535882742336/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/bne/

National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/biblioteca.nacional.portugal/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/BibliotecaNationala/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/BibNatRo/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/BNCFirenze/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/bncrm
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/bksh.al
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/bnbiblioteka?_rdc=1&_rdr
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/bibliothequebnf
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/bnluxembourg
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/maltalibraries/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/britishlibrary
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/DetKglBibliotek/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/DeutscheNationalbibliothek/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/rahvusraamatukogu/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/Kansalliskirjasto/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/KB.nationalebibliotheek/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/KBR-276661032407218/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/kungligabiblioteket/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/landsbokasafn/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/lnb.lv
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/NationalLibraryofIreland/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/Landesbibliothek/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/nacionalebiblioteka

National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/az.nat.lib/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/TCKulturTurizm
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/nacionalnabibliotekacg
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/nskzq/
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ca/">https://www.facebook.com/NarodnaUniverzitetnaKnjizni ca/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/narodni.knihovna
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/nasionalbiblioteket/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/nemzetikonyvtar
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/nationalbibliothek/
National Libraries	<a href="https://www.facebook.com/schweizerische.nationalbibli
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National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/slovenskanarodnakniznica
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/nationallibraryofgreece/
National Libraries	
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/nbsrb/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/nbkmbg/
National Libraries	<a href="https://www.facebook.com/pages/Vernadsky-National-
Library-of-
Ukraine/106113226086518?rf=226987283984096">https://www.facebook.com/pages/Vernadsky-National- Library-of- Ukraine/106113226086518?rf=226987283984096
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/prlib
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/Leninka.ru/
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/nlr.ru

National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/%D5%80%D5%A1%D5%B5%D5%A1%D5%BD%D5%BF%D5%A1%D5%B6%D5%AB-%D5%A1%D5%A6%D5%A3%D5%A1%D5%B5%D5%AB%D5%B6-%D5%A3%D6%80%D5%A1%D5%A4%D5%A1%D6%80%D5%A1%D5%B6-603668326354243
National Libraries	https://www.facebook.com/NATIONALPARLIAMENTARYLIBRARYOFGEORGIA/
National Theaters	http://www.facebook.com/officialTeatriKombetar/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/LandestheaterLinz
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/SchauspielhausGraz
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/theatredeliege.be/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/theatrelaboratorysfumato/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/dktdimovpp
National Theaters	http://www.facebook.com/hnk.hr/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/cinohraND
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/Mestskadivadlaprazska
National Theaters	http://www.facebook.com/ThocOfficial
National Theaters	
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/Kansallisteatteri/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/Cdn.Nancy.Lorraine.la.Manufacture
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/odeon.theatre.europe/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/MarjanishviliDramaTheatre/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/Meskhishvili-Theatre-მესხიშვილის-თეატრი-113616115371346/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/DeutschesTheater/

National Theaters	http://www.facebook.com/TheaterHeidelberg/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/NTNGreece
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/magyarszinhaz/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/home.php#!/pages/Szombat-hely-Hungary/Weores-Sandor-Szinhaz/158105264224853
National Theaters	http://www.facebook.com/TeatroDueParma/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/teatrokoreja/
National Theaters	
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/pages/Homo-Novus-festival/150213111673973?ref=ts
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/Teatras.It/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/LesTheatresVDL/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/EscherTheater/
National Theaters	http://www.facebook.com/TeatruMalta/
National Theaters	http://www.facebook.com/detnorsketeatret/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/teatropole/
National Theaters	https://web.facebook.com/StaryTeatr?_rdr
National Theaters	https://facebook.com/TeatroNacionalSaoJoao
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/TNDMII
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/tntimisoara/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/tadpitesti
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/npbqd
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/Jugoslovenskodramskopozoriste/
National Theaters	http://www.facebook.com/sndcinohra/

National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/djptrnava/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/presernovogledalisce
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/sng.novagorica/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/goteborgs.stadsteater
National Theaters	http://www.facebook.com/detoneelmakerij
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/teatrDakh/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/molodyytheatre/
National Theaters	https://www.facebook.com/belarusfreetheatre/
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/parcocolosseo/
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/StonehengeEH
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/pontdugard/
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/TheRomanBaths
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/newgrangeandknowth/
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/ArenesdeNimes
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/parcodeitempli/
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/people/Delphi-Culture/100057378762867/
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/skelligmichaelworldheritagesite
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/KernavesMuziejus
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/login/?next=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.facebook.com%2Fcarnuntum.at%2F
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/ParcarcheologiqueeuropeendeBliesbruckReinheim/
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/museudocoa
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/MACempuries/

Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/pompeiisoprintendenza/
Archeological Sites	https://www.facebook.com/NaHradHelfstyn/?rf=156575211847771
Fashion GLAMs	catwalkpictures
Fashion GLAMs	modemuseumhasselt
Fashion GLAMs	momuantwerp
Fashion GLAMs	fashionandlacemuseum
Fashion GLAMs	PalaisGalliera
Fashion GLAMs	museeyslparis
Fashion GLAMs	citedentelle
Fashion GLAMs	museodellacalzaturaVFR
Fashion GLAMs	Fondazione Gianfranco Ferré
Fashion GLAMs	fondazionefila
Fashion GLAMs	itsweb.org
Fashion GLAMs	armanisilos
Fashion GLAMs	museodeltessuto
Fashion GLAMs	fondazioneferragamo
Fashion GLAMs	Modemuze
Fashion GLAMs	textielmuseum
Fashion GLAMs	Textile Research Centre
Fashion GLAMs	cmwllodz
Fashion GLAMs	mudemuseulisboa
Fashion GLAMs	museodeltraje
Fashion GLAMs	cristobalbalenciagamuseoa

Fashion GLAMs	cristobalbalenciagamuseoa
Fashion GLAMs	FashionMuseum
Fashion GLAMs	fashionandtextilemuseum
Fashion GLAMs	westminsternsweararchive
Fashion GLAMs	fondazionezegna
Fashion GLAMs	YorkshireFashionArchive
Most visited EU Museums	museelouvre
Most visited EU Museums	museeorsay
Most visited EU Museums	rijksmuseum
Most visited EU Museums	museoguggenheim
Most visited EU Museums	museoreinasofia
Most visited EU Museums	museoprado
Most visited EU Museums	vaticanmuseums
Most visited EU Museums	museothyssen
Most visited EU Museums	le_grand_palais
Most visited EU Museums	centrepompidou
Most visited EU Museums	museeorangerie
Most visited EU Museums	kunsthistorischesmuseumvienna
Most visited EU Museums	museupicasso
Most visited EU Museums	fundacao_serralves
Most visited EU Museums	fondationbeyeler
Most visited EU Museums	stedelijkmuseum
Most visited EU Museums	smkmuseum
Most visited EU Museums	belvederemuseum

Most visited EU Museums	quaibranlı
Most visited EU Museums	staedelmuseum
Most visited EU Museums	fondationlv
Most visited EU Museums	zamekkrolewskiwarszawa
Most visited EU Museums	mucem_officiel
Most visited EU Museums	ngprague
Most visited EU Museums	fineartsbelgium
Most visited EU Museums	museuberardo
Most visited EU Museums	dhmberlin
Most visited EU Museums	galleriadellaccademiafirenze
Most visited EU Museums	uffizigallery
Most visited EU Museums	museoegizio
Most visited EU Museums	museoetruscovillagiulia
Most visited EU Museums	museoarcheologiconapoli
Most visited EU Museums	macromuseoroma
Most visited EU Museums	museomaxxi
Museums with Virtual Tour	museelouvre
Museums with Virtual Tour	vangoghmuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	metmuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	hermitage_museum
Museums with Virtual Tour	themuseumofmodernart
Museums with Virtual Tour	chateauversailles
Museums with Virtual Tour	britishmuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	museeorsay

Museums with Virtual Tour	guggenheim
Museums with Virtual Tour	uffizigalleries
Museums with Virtual Tour	rijksmuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	masp
Museums with Virtual Tour	museoprado
Museums with Virtual Tour	ngadc
Museums with Virtual Tour	gettymuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	annefrankhouse_official
Museums with Virtual Tour	museupicasso
Museums with Virtual Tour	smithsoniannmnh
Museums with Virtual Tour	mmcakorea
Museums with Virtual Tour	afmuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	dalimuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	museoegizio
Museums with Virtual Tour	vaticanmuseums
Museums with Virtual Tour	pinacotecabrera
Museums with Virtual Tour	womenshistory
Museums with Virtual Tour	mnantropologia
Museums with Virtual Tour	ghibli.museum
Museums with Virtual Tour	pergamonmuseumberlin
Museums with Virtual Tour	guggenheimbilbao
Museums with Virtual Tour	museicapitolini

List's name	Instagram Account
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Most Visited EU Museums	museelouvre
Most Visited EU Museums	museeorsay
Most Visited EU Museums	rijksmuseum
Most Visited EU Museums	museoguggenheim
Most Visited EU Museums	museoreinasofia
Most Visited EU Museums	museoprado
Most Visited EU Museums	vaticanmuseums
Most Visited EU Museums	museothyssen
Most Visited EU Museums	le_grand_palais
Most Visited EU Museums	centrepompidou
Most Visited EU Museums	museeorangerie
Most Visited EU Museums	kunsthistorischesmuseumvienna
Most Visited EU Museums	museupicasso
Most Visited EU Museums	fundacao_serralves
Most Visited EU Museums	fondationbeyeler
Most Visited EU Museums	stedelijkmuseum
Most Visited EU Museums	smkmuseum
Most Visited EU Museums	belvederemuseum
Most Visited EU Museums	quaibranly
Most Visited EU Museums	staedelmuseum
Most Visited EU Museums	fondationlv
Most Visited EU Museums	zamekkrolewskiwarszawa
Most Visited EU Museums	mucem_officiel
Most Visited EU Museums	ngprague

Most Visited EU Museums	fineartsbelgium
Most Visited EU Museums	museuberardo
Most Visited EU Museums	dhmberlin
Most Visited EU Museums	galleriadellaccademiafirenze
Most Visited EU Museums	uffizigallery
Most Visited EU Museums	museoegizio
Most Visited EU Museums	museoetruscovillagiulia
Most Visited EU Museums	museoarcheologiconapoli
Most Visited EU Museums	macromuseoroma
Most Visited EU Museums	museomaxxi
Museums with Virtual Tour	museelouvre
Museums with Virtual Tour	vangoghmuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	metmuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	hermitage_museum
Museums with Virtual Tour	themuseumofmodernart
Museums with Virtual Tour	chateauversailles
Museums with Virtual Tour	britishmuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	museeorsay
Museums with Virtual Tour	guggenheim
Museums with Virtual Tour	uffizigalleries
Museums with Virtual Tour	rijksmuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	masp
Museums with Virtual Tour	museoprado
Museums with Virtual Tour	ngadc

Museums with Virtual Tour	gettymuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	annefrankhouse_official
Museums with Virtual Tour	museupicasso
Museums with Virtual Tour	smithsoniannmnh
Museums with Virtual Tour	mmcakorea
Museums with Virtual Tour	afmuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	dalimuseum
Museums with Virtual Tour	museoegizio
Museums with Virtual Tour	vaticanmuseums
Museums with Virtual Tour	pinacotecabrera
Museums with Virtual Tour	womenshistory
Museums with Virtual Tour	mnantropologia
Museums with Virtual Tour	ghibli.museum
Museums with Virtual Tour	pergamonmuseumberlin
Museums with Virtual Tour	guggenheimbilbao
Museums with Virtual Tour	museicapitolini
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/bbc_archive/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/cinamatekbe/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/archives_state_agency_bulgaria/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/hrvatski_drzavni_arhiv/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/narodnifilmovyarchiv/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/rigsarkivet/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/rahvuserhiiv/

Archives	https://www.instagram.com/ina.fr/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/archivesnatfr
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/das_bundesarchiv/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/bauhaus_archiv/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/tainiothikiqr/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/mnleveltar/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/narireland/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/archiviocentrale_official/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/archivioluce/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/centrinisarchyvas/
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Archives	https://www.instagram.com/arkivverket/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/fina.gov.pl/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/narodowe_archiwum_cyfrowe/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/zgodovinskiarhivljubljana/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/archivolafuente/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/archivolafuente/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/cinemathequesuisse/
Archives	https://www.instagram.com/ch_bundesarchiv/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/bne_biblioteca/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/bibliotecanationala/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/bibliotecanazionale/

National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/bibliotecanazionaleroma/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/national_library_of_albania/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/bibliotekarodowa/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/labnf/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/bnl.lux/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/maltalibraries/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/britishlibrary/?hl=it
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/detkglbibliotek/
National Libraries	
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/rahvusraamatukogu/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/kansalliskirjasto/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/koninklijkebibliotheek/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/kbrbe/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/lnb.lv/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/nationallibraryofireland/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/landesbibliothek_liechtenstein/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/nacionalinebiblioteka/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/milli_kitabxana_/?igshid=14t378hhpgdjd
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/tckulturturizm/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/nsk_zagreb/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/knjiznicanuk/

National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/nasjonalbiblioteket/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/nemzetikonyvtar/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/nationalbibliothek/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/swissnationallibrary/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/slovenskanarodnakniznica/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/national_library_of_greece/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/narodnabibliotekasrbije/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/national.library.bulgaria/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/presidential_library/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/leninka_official/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/national_library_of_russia/
National Libraries	https://www.instagram.com/nationallibraryofarmenia/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/teatrikombetar.tk/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/schauspielhaus_graz/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/theatredeliege/
National Theaters	http://www.instagram.com/croatiannationaltheatre/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/cinohrand/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/abckomedierokoko/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/theatre.manufacture
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/theatreodeon/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/kotemarjanishvilitheatre/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/kutaisi_dramatheatre/

National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/deutschestheaterberlin/
National Theaters	http://www.instagram.com/theater_und_orchester_hd/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/ntngreece/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/magyarszinhaz/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/weoressandorszinhaz/
National Theaters	http://instagram.com/teatrodueparma
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/teatrokoreja/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/homonovusfestival/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/teatras.lt/?hl=en
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/lestheatresvdl/
National Theaters	http://www.instagram.com/teatrumalta/
National Theaters	http://www.instagram.com/detnorsketeatret/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/teatropole/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/stary_teatr/
National Theaters	https://instagram.com/teatronacionalsojoao
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/tndmii/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/teatrulnationaltimisoara
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/narodno_pozoriste_u_beo_gradu/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/jdpbgd/?hl=en
National Theaters	http://instagram.com/cinohrasnd/?hl=sk
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/djptrnava/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/presernovo/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/GoteborgsStadsteater/

National Theaters	http://www.instagram.com/toneelmakerij/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/molodyytheatre/
National Theaters	https://www.instagram.com/belarusfreetheatre/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/parcocolosseo/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/stonehenge/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/pontdugard/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/theromanbaths/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/newgrangeandknowth/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/arenesdenimes/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/valledeitempliofficial/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/delphiculture/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/kernave/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/roemerstadt_carnuntum/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/museudocoa/?hl=pt
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/pompeii_parco_archeologico/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/hrad_helfstyn/
Archeological Sites	https://www.instagram.com/theatreantiquedorange/
Fashion GLAMs	catwalkpictures
Fashion GLAMs	modemuseum_hasselt
Fashion GLAMs	momuantwerp
Fashion GLAMs	fashionandlacemuseum
Fashion GLAMs	palais_galliera

Fashion GLAMs	museeyslparis
Fashion GLAMs	cite_dentelle_mode
Fashion GLAMs	museodellacalzaturavfr
Fashion GLAMs	fondazionegianfrancoferre
Fashion GLAMs	fondazione_fila_museum
Fashion GLAMs	itsplatform
Fashion GLAMs	museodeltessuto
Fashion GLAMs	fondazioneferragamo
Fashion GLAMs	modemuze.nl
Fashion GLAMs	textielmuseum
Fashion GLAMs	textileresearchcentre
Fashion GLAMs	centralnemuzeumwlokiennictwa
Fashion GLAMs	mudemuseu
Fashion GLAMs	museodeltraje
Fashion GLAMs	crislobalbalenciagamuseoa
Fashion GLAMs	crislobalbalenciagamuseoa
Fashion GLAMs	fashion_museum_bath
Fashion GLAMs	fashiontextilemuseum
Fashion GLAMs	menswear_archive
Fashion GLAMs	casazegna

Fashion GLAMs	yorkshirefashionarchive
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